

D7.4 Final Dissemination Report and Exploitation Roadmap

**Final Dissemination Report and
Exploitation Roadmap**

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Abstract	The MSP4BIO project recognised the effective implementation of a strategic communication and dissemination plan as a central pillar of its' success and achieved strong and wide-reaching outreach, surpassing initial KPIs and ensuring high visibility for its results. The project website became a central hub with 65

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blog posts and over 35,000 visits, supported by effective cross-platform promotion. LinkedIn proved to be the most impactful social media channel, attracting over 800 followers and strong engagement from research, policy, and education professionals. Participation in more than 120 events enabled direct knowledge exchange with over 15,000 stakeholders, while targeted activities like the Science-Policy Think Tanks and validation workshops helped strengthen policy relevance. Strategic collaboration with related initiatives and features on prominent platforms such as CINEA, EU MSP Platform, and Mission Ocean significantly expanded the project's reach, leading to an overall outreach audience of 640,000 people. With collaborative tools like newsletters, factsheets, policy briefs, and scientific publications in place - even beyond the project's lifespan - MSP4BIO is well positioned to support upcoming EU policy processes and ensure long-term impact. Building on this strong dissemination foundation, the Exploitation Roadmap presented in the second part of the deliverable outlines how MSP4BIO's tools, knowledge, and policy recommendations can continue to be used, scaled, and adapted. It captures both the exploitation activities already undertaken and future pathways to ensure the project's legacy. The roadmap provides guidance on how diverse stakeholders—including MSP planners, MPA managers, regional authorities, and EU institutions—can adopt and operationalize MSP4BIO outputs to strengthen biodiversity integration in Maritime Spatial Planning across Europe and beyond.

Keywords

Dissemination, Exploitation, Legacy, sustainability of results, Roadmap

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Acronyms

KPIs – Key Performance Indicators
EU – European Union
EC – European Commission
WP – Work Package
CoP – Community of Practices
GDPR – General Data Protection Regulation
DST(s) – Decision Support Tool(s)
EBA – Ecosystem-based Approach
ESE Framework – Ecological-Socio-Economic Framework
EUBS2030 – EU Biodiversity Strategy 2030
MPAs – Marine Protected Areas
MSFD – Marine Strategy Framework Directive
MSP – Maritime Spatial Planning
MSPD – Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
NGO- Non-Governmental Organization
DG – Directorate General
MPA CN – MPA Community Network
KERs – Key Exploitable Results

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Executive Summary

The MSP4BIO project recognised the effective implementation of a strategic communication and dissemination plan as a central pillar of its' success and achieved strong and wide-reaching outreach, surpassing initial KPIs and ensuring high visibility for its results. The project website became a central hub with 65 blog posts and over 35,000 visits, supported by effective cross-platform promotion. LinkedIn proved to be the most impactful social media channel, attracting over 800 followers and strong engagement from research, policy, and education professionals. Participation in more than 120 events enabled direct knowledge exchange with over 15,000 stakeholders, while targeted activities like the Science-Policy Think Tanks and validation workshops helped strengthen policy relevance. Strategic collaboration with related initiatives and features on prominent platforms such as CINEA, EU MSP Platform, and Mission Ocean significantly expanded the project's reach, leading to an overall outreach audience of 640,000 people. With collaborative tools like newsletters, factsheets, policy briefs, and scientific publications in place - even beyond the project's lifespan - MSP4BIO is well positioned to support upcoming EU policy processes and ensure long-term impact.

Building on this strong dissemination foundation, the Exploitation Roadmap presented in the second part of the deliverable outlines how MSP4BIO's tools, knowledge, and policy recommendations can continue to be used, scaled, and adapted. It captures both the exploitation activities already undertaken and future pathways to ensure the project's legacy. The roadmap provides guidance on how diverse stakeholders—including MSP planners, MPA managers, regional authorities, and EU institutions—can adopt and operationalize MSP4BIO outputs to strengthen biodiversity integration in Maritime Spatial Planning across Europe and beyond.

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1. Introduction

As pressures on European sea's intensify - including climate change and competing economic interests – Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) emerges as a vital and integrative tool. MSP has the potential to enable more coordinated, adaptive and sustainable use of marine resources aligning ecological integrity with economic development and societal needs. A key strength of MSP lies in its ability to bring together diverse sectors, governance levels, and ecological priorities within a unified, cohesive planning framework. Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) count as the most commonly used tool to safeguard biodiversity and align conservation objectives with the blue economy. When well-designed and managed, MPAs support ecosystem resilience, maintain marine ecosystem services and ultimately enhance human well-being.

Building on this foundation, MSP4BIO – funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe research programme (Grant Agreement 101060707) – aims to demonstrate how science-based MSP can drive the protection of marine ecosystems across Europe. Over the course of three years, the project developed an integrated, modular Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) framework that links cutting-edge environmental science with socio-economic priorities—helping to embed biodiversity and climate resilience directly into maritime decision-making. Tested in six distinct pilot sites in five European sea basins, MSP4BIO actively engaged MSP planners and MPA managers through participatory Communities of Practice, applying tools like PlanWise4Blue and the Area-based Conservation Planner to build ownership and deliver results that can inform site specific but also broader policy decisions.

Aligned with the 2030 EU Biodiversity Strategy, the EU Green Deal, and the Convention on Biological Diversity post-2020 framework, the project strengthens the integration of maritime spatial planning and area-based conservation to drive a coherent, biodiversity-inclusive MSP approach for Europe's seas.

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2. Objectives and vision

The main objective of the MSP4BIO Final Dissemination Report and Exploitation Roadmap is to showcase the successful implementation of the project's communication and dissemination strategy while ensuring its tools, knowledge, and policy recommendations continue to support the integration of biodiversity into Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) across Europe and beyond. The report highlights the project's impact and illustrates how its outcomes can be adopted by a wide range of users, including planners, MPA managers, authorities, and marine stakeholders at national and regional levels. It also underscores the need for sustained cross-sectoral collaboration and coherent governance.

This deliverable supports the strategic uptake, transfer, and long-term application of MSP4BIO results beyond the project's duration. It is intended to enable institutions, policymakers, practitioners, and researchers to operationalise the project's outputs in advancing biodiversity integration in MSP and in contributing to the EU 2030 Biodiversity Strategy, including the 30x30 conservation targets. It emphasises accessibility and adaptability, ensuring that MSP4BIO tools can be applied in a range of geographic and institutional settings.

The report also offers guidance on aligning project outcomes with future research and funding, promoting the use of EU funding instruments for implementation in planning, restoration, and climate adaptation. Finally, it calls for continuous stakeholder engagement, knowledge exchange, and institutional learning to monitor and sustain the project's long-term impact.

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3. Final Dissemination Report

3.1 Communication and Dissemination Strategy

In the MSP4BIO project, communication, dissemination, and exploitation were designed as interlinked and mutually reinforcing components rather than separate workstreams. This integrated approach ensured consistency in messaging, alignment of timing and content, and a clear pathway from awareness to uptake. Communication activities supported visibility and stakeholder interest, with dissemination enabling targeted sharing of knowledge and results, and exploitation focusing on practical use and long-term impact. This strategy proved essential for turning technical results into actionable insights, sustaining stakeholder engagement and supporting long-term legacy beyond the project's duration.

3.1.1 Visual Identity and project dissemination outlets

As a key aspect of its mission, the MSP4BIO project placed significant emphasis on the dissemination and exploitation of its activities and results, aiming to foster an ongoing dialogue with potential users, diverse audiences, and experts in maritime spatial planning (MSP) and marine biodiversity conservation — both during the project and beyond its lifetime. Ensuring broad access and engagement, MSP4BIO made its outcomes available through a variety of outlets, including official project presentations, public deliverables and their summaries, the project website, social media platforms, conferences, and other communication channels.

To support and enhance the visibility and recognition of these dissemination efforts, the project developed a distinctive and coherent visual identity. This included a characteristic logo, colour palette, European Commission (EC) emblem, funding statement and disclaimer, and a unified graphic style (see Figure 1). These visual elements were consistently applied across all project materials — such as the website, deliverable templates, webinar presentations, flyers, roll-ups, and policy briefs — ensuring recognisability and reinforcing the credibility of the project's outputs across all communication formats.

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LOGO USAGE

MASTER LOGO

USE: Main
BACKGROUND: White only

LOGO | MONOCHROME

USE: Specific cases if needed
BACKGROUND: White only

LOGO WHITE | MONOCHROME

USE: Photos/illustrations
BACKGROUND: Dark

LOGO BLACK | MONOCHROME

USE: For printing in black colour (B&W)
BACKGROUND: White only

CMYK: 75,46,0,55
RGB: 29,62,115
Web: 103E73
Pantone: 654 C

CMYK: 70, 0, 44, 0
RGB: 105, 201, 172
Web: 00C9AD
Pantone: 3265 C

100% 80% 60% 40% 20%

SECONDARY PALETTE

CMYK: 57,17,0,51
RGB: 54,105,126
Web: 36697E

CMYK: 0,29,71,54
RGB: 117,83,34
Web: 755322

CMYK: 28,13,0,30
RGB: 129,155,178
Web: 8198B2

CMYK: 0,54,61,36
RGB: 162,74,63
Web: A24A3F

CMYK: 39,3,0,29
RGB: 110,175,181
Web: 6EAFB5

CMYK: 0,27,69,23
RGB: 197,143,62
Web: C58F3E

CMYK: 31,0,5,16
RGB: 143,214,204
Web: 8FDBCC

CMYK: 0,31,74,6
RGB: 240,105,63
Web: F0A63F

CMYK: 7,1,0,5
RGB: 223,239,241
Web: DFEFF1

CMYK: 0,28,85,0
RGB: 255,184,38
Web: FF8B26

CMYK: 0,41,46,9
RGB: 233,138,126
Web: E98A7E

(a)

(b)

Figure 1 Overview of the visual identity of the project with (a) the MSP4BIO Logo versions including the master logo and monochrome versions and (b) the MSP4BIO colour palette with two primary colours (blue, green).

3.1.2 Communication materials

The dissemination strategy of the MSP4BIO project has been based on the D.7.1 and D.7.2 anchoring its own development in a diverse and comprehensive production and dissemination of communication materials. The selection and deployment of these communication tools have been crucial in elucidating the project's advancements and engaging a spectrum of stakeholders, including industry professionals, policymakers, and academic researchers.

As outlined in D.7.1 *Communication Strategy*, the project's dissemination toolkit includes ad-hoc tailored materials serving for diverse communication strategy and set targets outreach (see Figure 2). This organisation facilitates a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted aspects of MSP and marine biodiversity conservation.

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Figure 2 Communications material produced for the MSP4BIO website including project flyer, roll-up, project presentation, exclusive project videos, project posters and test site fiche.

1 Project Roll-up – The MSP4BIO project roll-up was designed with simplicity in mind, featuring a prominently displayed logo and project name for easy recognition. Its visually appealing design made it suitable for use at all major events attended by MSP4BIO partners, including project meetings, hosted workshops and conferences.

2 Test Site Fiches – MSP4BIO produced three fiches for the Graciosa Island, Romanian part of the Black Sea and Gulf of Cadiz Test Sites, to support simplified communication. These concise, low-barrier documents synthesise complex information, summarising key aspects of the project such as objectives, activities, results, and impacts for stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public.

1 Project Flyer – The MSP4BIO flyer was designed for quick overview of the project objectives, test sites and main expected outcomes, helping to disseminate information in a clear and accessible format. Flyers are ideal for both digital and physical distribution and were used at conferences, stakeholder meetings or workshops, supporting effective

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communication by combining brief text with visual elements to attract and inform a wide audience.

1 Project Poster – The MSP4BIO project poster summarises the core objectives, methods, test sites and expected outcomes of the project in a clear and engaging format. The poster was used at conferences, workshops, and exhibitions, supporting effective dissemination by combining concise text with graphics, charts, and visuals. This poster is designed to capture attention quickly, facilitate informal dialogue, and provide an accessible overview for diverse audiences, including researchers, policymakers, and the general public.

3 Project Slide Decks – The MSP4BIO slide deck was developed to present the project's goals, activities, and outcomes in a clear, engaging and concise format. These slide decks were used by MSP4BIO partner throughout the project to complement presentations and pitches of project components. To account for any advancements or changes in the project, MSP4BIO created three slide decks, one for each year of the project. However, all three decks were available for use throughout the project to have a satisfactory selection of project slides.

2 project templates (word/ppt) – Templates were used to ensure a coherent visual representation of the MSP4BIO project in documents and presentations. These templates were shared with all partners and used for the creation of deliverables, reports and other written materials (see Figure 4).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3 MSP4BIO (a) word template and (b) PowerPoint template

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3.1.3 Dissemination and exploitation materials

Briefs and Factsheets

As part of MSP4BIO’s dissemination strategy, a comprehensive repository of materials — including factsheets, briefs, and policy briefs — was developed to effectively promote and communicate the project’s outcomes to a broad and diverse audience. These materials distilled the key messages and findings from project deliverables into accessible, reader-friendly formats, ensuring that complex scientific and technical content could be easily understood and applied by non-specialist stakeholders. All materials are prominently available on the MSP4BIO website under the *Publications* section (see Figure 4), where they are organised by category for easy access. A rotating carousel for every category features the latest uploads up front, encouraging continued engagement from visitors. Additionally, printed versions of these materials were distributed at key events and conferences, helping to extend the project’s visibility beyond its duration and ensuring lasting impact among policymakers, practitioners, and other relevant stakeholders.

Figure 4 Publication page of the MSP4BIO website showing dissemination materials categorised in deliverables, factsheets, briefs, blog posts, newsletter, event reports, media and scientific publications.

Designed with clarity and impact in mind, the materials were tailored to three primary formats based on target audience and purpose:

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Factsheets – Two-page documents highlighting the most important insights, designed to quickly engage readers and direct them to more detailed resources.

A total of **13 factsheets** were developed to communicate key project outputs including [The MPA-MSP Guide](#), [Area-based Conservation in Europe](#), [the ESE Framework](#), [the Ecological Toolkit](#), [improved Ecological Criteria](#), [Trade-Off Scenarios for MPAs in MSP](#), [Socio-Economic Criteria for MPAs](#), [MSP4BIO's Data Compilation App](#). In addition, **five blue economy sectoral factsheets** — covering [Tourism](#), [Marine Non-Living Resources](#), [Fisheries](#), [Aquaculture](#), and [Renewable Energy](#) — were produced as part of Deliverable 4.2, *Guidelines for Strategic and Spatial Measures for the Nature-Inclusive Operation of the Blue Economy*.

Briefs – Concise booklets providing a general overview of deliverables, summarising key findings in a digestible format, linking to full deliverables and publications for wider dissemination.

To highlight specific outcomes produced in MSP4BIO, **three briefs** have been developed featuring innovative topics addressed in the project: [The comprehensive MSP-MPA Guide](#) (A Guide to support the integration of Marine Protected Areas into Maritime Spatial Planning), [Key Challenges and Strategic Needs for Integrating Biodiversity into MSP](#) and [Integrating Climate Change Scenarios in MPAs](#). These materials shed light on substantial outputs of MSP4BIO's work, attracting a broad audience to read more and explore related outcomes.

Policy Briefs – Targeted specifically at policymakers, these materials focused on the practical application of project tools and included actionable recommendations and proposed next steps for uptake in real-world contexts.

As part of Work Package 7 (WP7), **two targeted policy briefs** were developed to support policymakers working on MSP and marine conservation. One brief focused specifically on the [Baltic Sea region](#), responding to strong interest and positive feedback from the Baltic Sea Test Site, highlighting its potential for practical uptake. The second brief (Deliverable 7.5) offered actionable [guidance for more effective integration of MPAs into MSP processes](#).

In addition, **a cross-project policy brief** was produced as part of Deliverable 6.4, *Joint Policy Brief* incorporating **joint policy recommendations** developed in collaboration with sister and external projects addressing similar topics. These recommendations were shaped through a series of Science-Policy Think Tank meetings held during the project and are underpinned by strong scientific foundations (see section: Science-Policy Dialogue Think Tanks). As a result, they hold significant potential for policy influence and uptake across multiple governance levels.

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These outreach products substantially surpass initial project goals and provide an effective means of translating research into practice, increasing the visibility and accessibility of MSP4BIO’s tools and outcomes (see Table 1).

Table 1 Overview of KPIs (briefs and factsheets) with initially set goals and KPIs achieved

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	2+ briefs	3 briefs published
	3+ flyers/factsheets	13 Factsheets published
	2+ policy briefs	3 policy briefs created

Peer-reviewed Publications

MSP4BIO has made significant efforts in advancing the integration of marine protection within Maritime Spatial Planning, delivering tangible scientific and educational outcomes. Beyond producing a rich portfolio of deliverables, webinars, workshops, policy briefs, and factsheets, up until today, the project has generated **11 peer-reviewed articles** in leading scientific journals and books such as *Marine Policy*, *Marine Pollution Bulletin* or *Ocean & Coastal Management*, **one doctoral dissertation**, and **three master’s theses** demonstrating a strong commitment to both cutting-edge research and academic training. **Two more doctoral dissertations** and at least **seven scientific manuscripts** are still in preparation with a planned submission by the end of 2025 (see Table 2). The involvement of students through these theses not only contributes valuable insights to the project, but also actively builds expertise in the next generation of maritime spatial planners and marine scientists. Furthermore, MSP4BIO partners Helena Calado (UAc), Javier García Sanabria (UCA), and Riku Varjopuro (SYKE) are serving as guest editors for a forthcoming special issue of *npj Ocean Sustainability*, focusing on the critical role and growing potential of MSP in achieving marine biodiversity objectives.

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Figure 5 MSP4BIO publication section showing the scientific publication carousel with previews

To maximise accessibility aligned with the open access principles of the project, all scientific publications will be presented on the MSP4BIO website in an easy-to-navigate carousel format, with direct links to journals and downloadable full-text PDFs where open access is not available (see Figure 5). Further, project outcomes including publications and deliverables will be shared using platforms such as [Zenodo](#), [Marine Training](#), [the MPA Community Network](#), [Blue Bio Match](#), [the Nature Network](#), [the Blue Parks Community](#) and the [EU MSP Platform](#). Sharing MSP4BIO results across multiple external platforms supports the projects’ multi-level dissemination approach, ensuring that knowledge reached diverse audiences across local, national, and EU levels. This strategy aligned with open data principles and maximises uptake potential by increasing accessibility, visibility, and reuse of project outputs across sectors and governance scales. These achievements underline MSP4BIO’s role as a key driver of scientific progress and capacity building in marine biodiversity and spatial planning.

Table 2 List of publications published and planned coming out of the MSP4BIO project.

Status	Category	Publication
Published	Journal article	Vaher, A., Kotta, J., Szava-Kovats, R., Kaasik, A., Fetissof, M., Aps, R., et al. (2022). Assessing cumulative impacts of human-induced pressures on reef and sandbank habitats and associated biotopes in the northeastern Baltic Sea. <i>Marine Pollution Bulletin</i> 183, 114042. doi:10.1016/j.marpolbul.2022.114042
Published	Journal article	Cioffi, G., Sanabria, J. G., Sansolo, D. G., Pegorelli, C., and de Andrés, M. (2024). Assessing stakeholder participation in coastal zone management: Methodological proposal and its application in a case study from Cádiz Bay,

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		Andalusia (Spain). <i>Ocean and Coastal Management</i> 255, 107214. doi:10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2024.107214 .
Published	Journal article	Calado, H., Cervera-Núñez, C., Gutierrez, D., and Stojanovic (2025). Forging ahead: Climate-smart maritime spatial planning for the future. <i>Marine Policy</i> 171, 106503. doi:10.1016/j.marpol.2024.106503 .
Published	Journal article	de Queiroz, J. D., Gutierrez, D., and Calado, H. M. (2024). Trade-offs in marine policy decisions through the lens of literature. <i>Oceans</i> 5, 982–1007. doi:10.3390/oceans5040056 .
Published	Journal article	Calado, H., Gutierrez, D. & De Bruyn, A. Navigating trade-offs on conservation: the use of participatory mapping in maritime spatial planning. <i>npj Ocean Sustain</i> 4, 8 (2025). Doi:10.1038/s44183-025-00109-6
Published	Journal article	Pegorelli, C., De Andres, M., García-Onetti, J., Rayo, S., and García-Sanabria, J. (2024a). Marine Protected Areas as socio-economic systems: A method for defining socio-economic criteria in Marine Planning. <i>Frontiers in Marine Science</i> 11. doi:10.3389/fmars.2024.1358950 .
Published	Journal article	Frazão Santos, C., Wedding, L. M., Agardy, T., Reimer, J. M., Gissi, E., and Calado, H. (2025). Marine Spatial Planning and Marine Protected Area Planning are not the same and both are key for sustainability in a Changing Ocean. <i>npj Ocean Sustainability</i> 4. doi:10.1038/s44183-025-00119-4 .
Published	Journal article	Gutierrez, D., Calado, H., and García-Sanabria, J. (2023). A proposal for engagement in MPAs in areas beyond national jurisdiction: The case of macaronesia. <i>Science of The Total Environment</i> 854, 158711. doi:10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158711 .
Published	Journal article	Manea, E., Agardy, T., Bongiorni, L (2023). Link marine restoration to marine spatial planning through ecosystem-based management to maximize ocean regeneration. <i>Aquatic Conservation</i> . doi: 10.1002/aqc.3999
Published	Book Chapter	Blasco, J., Polette, M., Laiz, I., Calado, H. (Eds.). (2023). STOTEN Special issue: Blue knowledge generation for improving sustainable water and coastal management.
Published	Book Chapter	Calado, H., Vergílio, M., Moniz, F., Grimmel, H., Monwar, M.M., Papaioannou, E.A (2023). The Diverse Legal and Regulatory Framework for Marine Sustainability Policy in the North Atlantic – Horrendograms as Tools to Assist Circumnavigating Through a Sea of Different Maritime Policies. In: Partelow, S., Hadjimichael, M., Hornidge, AK. (eds) <i>Ocean Governance</i> .
Published	PhD dissertation	Mihhail Fetissov (2022). Spatial decision support systems for ecosystem-based marine management . PhD dissertation.

Published	MSc thesis	Joyce Dias Gois Rodrigues de Queiroz (2024). Toward Sustainable Conservation: Addressing Trade-offs in Marine Environment. Master thesis.
Published	MSc thesis	Silvia Rayo (2024). Analysis and proposals to guide, from an ecosystem-based approach, the development of sectors operating in European MPAs. Master thesis.
Published	MSc thesis	Nancy Cross (2025). Climate-smart marine spatial planning to support long-term conservation of marine biodiversity. Master thesis.
In Preparation	Journal article	Hoppit, G., Nurkse, K., Beleem, I., Cadoni, N., Crowe, T., Bekaert, M., Bongiorno, L., Dvorski, K., Frau, F., Jernberg, S., Krvarić, A., Kõivupuu, A., Malovrazić, N., Marchessaux, G., Perschke, M. J., Petersen, H. C., Organo Quintana, C., Raatikainen, K. J., Sará, G., Sicard, M., Stevens, M., Szava-Kovats, R., Vaher, A., Van Gerven, A., Barboza, F. R. (tbc). Enhancing Marine Protected Areas with Effective Ecological and Environmental Data Integration. <i>Ecological indicators</i> .
In Preparation	Journal article	Hoppit, G., Nurkse, K., Beleem, I., Cadoni, N., Crowe, T., Bekaert, M., Bongiorno, L., Dvorski, K., Everaert, G., Frau, F., Jernberg, S., Krvarić, A., Kõivupuu, A., Malovrazić, N., Marchessaux, G., Perschke, M. J., Petersen, H. C., Organo Quintana, C., Raatikainen, K. J., de Raedemacker, F., Sará, G., Sicard, M., Stevens, M., Szava-Kovats, R., Vaher, A., Van Gerven, A., Barboza, F. R. (tbc). How Ecological and Environmental Data Supports Marine Protected Area Processes. <i>Conservation Biology</i> .
In Preparation	Journal article	Reconciling ecological criteria for the prioritization, designation and monitoring of marine area-based management tools with a focus on functional aspects.
In Preparation	Journal article	Enhancing biodiversity protection in MSP: an Ecological-Socio-Economic management framework.
In Preparation	Journal article	Smart tools for preserved Seas: The MSP4BIO - Ecological Toolkit and real-world applications. npj Ocean Sustainability.
In Preparation	Journal article	Those who start well are halfway there”: Framing climate-smart management objectives for Marine Protected Areas and MSP. npj Ocean Sustainability.
In Preparation	Book Chapter	Bocci, M, Stojanovic, S (tbc). Strengthening Biodiversity Conservation in MSP in <i>in Ocean, Marine and Coastal Governance Vol 2. Climate Resilience, Nature-Based Solutions, and Ecosystem Adaptation</i> .
In Preparation	PhD dissertation	Camila Pegorelli (2025). Connecting People, Space, and Nature: A Governance Perspective on Ecosystem Services in MSP and MPAs. PhD dissertation.

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In Preparation	PhD dissertation	Volcy Boilevin (tbc): Analysis of marine biodiversity protection measures in maritime spatial planning documents. PhD dissertation.
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Table 3 Overview of KPI (scientific publications) with initially set goals and KPI achieved

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	2+ scientific manuscripts	11 peer-reviewed articles

3.2 MSP4BIO website

3.2.1 Design & User Experience

The [MSP4BIO website](#) — built on a modern, responsive content-management framework — functions as the project’s primary digital gateway centralising all facets of its maritime spatial planning work and ensuring stakeholders have seamless access to up-to-date information, data, publications and outreach tools. The website was designed with a strong focus on user experience, ensuring that complex content is accessible, engaging, and easy to navigate. Key design features support intuitive exploration of the project’s pilot sites, thematic pillars, and outputs across all user groups and devices:

Consistent Navigation: A fixed top-bar menu remains visible as users scroll, with drop-down submenus for quick access to pilot-site pages and thematic content.

Visual Hierarchy: High-contrast headings, color-coded pillar icons and clear “read-more” buttons guide readers through complex material.

Interactive Elements: From the pilot-site map to infographic sliders in the Pillars section, interactive widgets both inform and invite exploration.

Mobile-First Approach: Optimized layouts ensure readability and functionality across devices — from desktops to smartphones — supporting on-the-go researchers and practitioners.

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Figure 6 Insights from the MSP4BIO website.

Carefully structured to mirror the project’s thematic pillars, activities, and outputs; the site comprises eight core sections (Home, About, Pilots, Pillars, ESE, Partners, Publications and News) plus a suite of **seven detailed pilot-site pages including designated StoryMaps**, and a total of **12 main pages** (see Table 4). Additionally, a footer section has been equipped with the main contact details, the GDPR followed and the Imprint of the website.

Table 4 Overview of MSP4BIO website’s 12 main pages

<p>HOME</p>	<p>An attractive dashboard introduces visitors to MSP4BIO’s mission and latest highlights. Prominent callouts drive users to new publications, featured news items and upcoming events, while a rotating banner showcases MSP4BIO’s research pillars, pilots and partners.</p>
<p>ABOUT</p>	<p>This section lays out the project’s rationale, objectives, and methodology. An interactive banner gives easy access to MSP4BIO’s four thematic pillars, the projects pilots and its sister projects alongside a succinct interactive timeline providing key insights of project phases and redirects to eminent outputs.</p>
<p>PILOTS</p>	<p>This section provides an overview of the MSP4BIO test sites including key facts about the pilots. At its heart there is an interactive map plotting all six test sites (Belgian North Sea, Gdańsk Bay, Bay of Cádiz, Bulgarian Black Sea + two Romanian Black Sea, Northwest Mediterranean, and Graciosa Island). By clicking each marker, a dedicated pilot-site page opens with site descriptions, objectives, preliminary findings</p>

	and links to raw data. By hovering over the <i>pilots</i> section on the menu bar, you can explore the seven preliminary StoryMaps created by T.7.4 which introduce each test site and present the outcomes of the second CoP interactions, as well as an additional StoryMap providing an overview of test site results (see section 3.2.2).
PILLARS	A deep-dive into the four research themes guides users through objectives, methodologies and cross-pillar synergies.
ESE	As a major outcome of the MSP4BIO project, the ESE Framework is prominently highlighted on the website with its own dedicated section, easily accessible via the menu bar. This section introduces the framework's objectives, purpose, and key features, and directs users to the full ESE platform . Further, this section features an engaging infographic outlining the core steps of the framework in a clear and accessible format.
PARTNERS	Profiles of the 17 participating institutions appear here, complete with logos, role descriptions and website links. A sub-section lists the Project Advisory Board members, showcasing their expertise and affiliations.
PUBLICATIONS	This section is structured into three main subsections: Publications, Data Compilation, and Briefs. The Publications subsection includes all project-related outputs such as deliverables, factsheets, briefs, blog posts, newsletters, event reports, as well as media and scientific publications. By hovering over the "Publications" tab in the menu bar, users can access the second category, Data Compilation, an interactive RShiny app developed by Task 2.1. This tool provides access to datasets that have been compiled and reused throughout the project. The Briefs category offers a direct link to the list of briefs contained within the Publications section.
NEWS	A chronological feed of announcements and blog posts keeps the community informed of new results, events recaps, interviews and media coverage. Each item includes social-share buttons to amplify reach.
EVENTS	An integrated calendar provides an overview of past webinars, workshops, and conference participations. Each event page includes a description, agenda (when available), and registration links.
CONTACT (Footer)	This static page includes the project contacts details and the newsletter sign-up field, ensuring continuous engagement with MSP4BIO's mailing list.
IMPRINT (Footer)	This section covers the website whole imprint and site credits, alongside the newsletter sign-up field, ensuring continuous engagement with MSP4BIO's mailing list.
DATA PROTECTION (Footer)	This page covers GDPR compliance, terms of usage of the user data, alongside the newsletter sign-up field, ensuring continuous engagement with MSP4BIO's mailing list.

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3.2.2 Visualisation tools

Task 7.4, in collaboration with test side leads, has produced several StoryMaps using the ArcGIS StoryMaps tool to communicate the main results and outcomes from each test site. Initially, one StoryMap per test site (two for the Western Black Sea) were produced to introduce the test sites and present the outcomes of the second CoP interactions. These StoryMaps presented background information on the main ecological features and human pressures at each test site accompanied by interactive maps displaying associated spatial data. The spatial data resulting from the CoP interaction, such as the results of the participatory mapping exercises collected using the SeaSketch tool, were then displayed directly in the StoryMaps. Links to the StoryMaps were added to the website, and they were publicised on social media.

An [additional StoryMap](#)¹ based on D5.3 was created towards the end of the project to communicate MSP4BIO's final outcomes in the test sites (site specific solutions) and real-world impacts. This StoryMap is organised into sections by test site and shows the input data and results and recommendations from each site. It was publicised on MSP4BIO's social media and was shared during the final event held in Venice, 2-4th of July 2025.

Figure 7 QR Code to the MSP4BIO StoryMaps

3.7.1 Website Blog Posts

To maintain continuous engagement with the MSP4BIO community and offer an accessible entry point for newcomers, the project's website featured a regularly updated newsfeed section. This platform hosts a series of blog posts designed to communicate key developments, insights from deliverables, and summaries of recent events and

¹ <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/faf55224ffaa4fea893bc2f70ebf4b88>

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activities. Over the project lifetime, a total of **65 blog posts** were published, serving as a transparent and timely channel for sharing progress with a broader audience. The blog posts were created to be both informative and engaging, helping to bridge the gap between technical outcomes and practical understanding. Each blog post included a clear title, a cover image, and an interactive call-to-action button inviting visitors to explore the full content on a separate page. The most recent blog posts are displayed at the top of the page, ensuring that new updates remained visible and accessible to users. This ongoing newsfeed not only supported regular Project outreach but also contributed to building a dynamic and informative digital presence for MSP4BIO.

Figure 8 MSP4BIO news feed and blog post insights

3.2.3 Overall Website Outreach

The MSP4BIO website has substantially outperformed its initial visibility targets (see Figure 9). Whereas the proposal established a goal of 3 000 page views, the platform has (to date) over **12 000 recorded unique visits** and more than **35 000 total clicks** (see Table 5). The homepage continues to serve as the principal gateway, attracting the highest proportion of traffic and effectively directing users to the core project content. Notably, the *About* and *Publication* sections emerged as the most visited areas of the site, validating MSP4BIO’s dissemination and exploitation strategy by confirming strong interest of visitors in exploring the project’s rationale and perusing its outputs. Visitors spent an average of nearly two minutes per session, frequently navigating to core project materials. Deliverables were accessed over 400 times, and **684 documents were downloaded** indicating active interest in the project's outputs. By combining a robust publications archive with a real-time news feed and events calendar, the MSP4BIO website doubles as both a **repository** — safeguarding data, deliverables and reading materials — and a **dissemination hub**, broadcasting project developments and catalysing stakeholder participation. The integrated newsletter form and social-media

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links (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) further extended MSP4BIO’s outreach, ensuring that its scientific innovations and policy recommendations reach a broad, engaged audience.

Figure 9 MSP4BIO Website metrics

Table 5 Overview of set KPI’s and achievements for the MSP4BIO website

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	3,000 visits	35,000 visits

The MSP4BIO website attracted visitors from **over 80 countries**, significantly extending the project’s visibility beyond European borders, highlighting its global relevance. While **Ireland, Spain, Italy, and Germany** generated the highest levels of traffic, the demographic analysis revealed substantial interest from outside EU, indicating the project’s ability to resonate with a broad international audience. This widespread engagement reflects not only the relevance of MSP4BIO’s underlying topics — marine biodiversity and spatial planning — but also the effectiveness of its digital outreach (see Figure 8). On another note, communication efforts of MSP4BIO partners were clearly reflected in the top 3 countries (Germany, Italy and Belgium) of returning visits to the website with well-known institutions of the project pushing for continual visibility. These results demonstrate robust engagement with MSP4BIO’s thematic pillars, pilot sites and deliverables, reinforcing the site’s role as both an information repository and a dissemination hub.

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Figure 10 Geographical dispersion of (a) MSP4BIO website visitors and (b) top 3 countries (Germany, Italy, Belgium) of returning users

3.3 Social Media Presence and Outreach

Recognising the vital role of social media in modern communication, MSP4BIO placed strong emphasis on maintaining a consistent and engaging presence across relevant platforms throughout the project. Social media channels were **launched on LinkedIn, YouTube, BlueBioMatch and X (formerly known as Twitter)** and strategically used to share regular updates on project progress, promote newly submitted deliverables, highlight blog posts, announce upcoming events, and disseminate publications and other key news. This continual online presence not only helped build awareness and interest in the project but also served as an effective gateway to the MSP4BIO website, which functioned as the central repository for project outputs and resources. By directing traffic to the website, social media supported broader dissemination goals, increased accessibility of results, and fostered ongoing engagement with stakeholders, partners, and the wider public.

3.3.1 MSP4BIO Social Media Platforms

MSP4BIO sustained a strong social media presence throughout the project, with [LinkedIn](#) and [X \(Twitter\)](#) functioning as main platforms for community engagement, collectively gaining **over 1000 followers** throughout the project (see Figure 9). From September 2023, MSP4BIO also hosted a project site on [BlueBioMatch](#), an EU open community designed to empower and connect blue bioeconomy actors throughout Europe and partners are active members of the [MPA Community Network Working Group](#) – sharing insights, events and more. **LinkedIn**, in particular, turned out to be an instrumental platform in reaching stakeholders, promoting project updates, and directing traffic to the MSP4BIO website, explaining why it is the only platform reaching the initial KPI of 500 followers (see Figure 11a). With an increasing number of partners and similar initiatives leaving **X** throughout the project, **LinkedIn** turned into the project's focus platform.

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Number of followers and post impressions showed a consistent upward trend, with a notable increase from April 2024 onwards. Posts were carefully crafted with social media best practices in mind, including optimal timing, post length, and concise, engaging messaging to maximise visibility and leverage platform algorithms. This targeted approach significantly contributed to raising awareness of MSP4BIO’s activities, fostering engagement with the wider community, and reinforcing the project’s role in the broader maritime spatial planning and biodiversity conservation landscape. On LinkedIn alone, the project published **190 posts**, resulting in over **300 reposts** and a total of over **60000 impressions** demonstrating strong content resonance and audience engagement. Collectively, MSP4BIO created and published **581 social media posts** informing, engaging and raising awareness about key topics of the project (see Figure 11b).

Table 6 Overview of set KPI and achievements for MSP4BIO’s social media platforms

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	500 followers/platform	864 followers on LinkedIn

Figure 11 (a) Project followers and (b) direct project posts across MSP4BIO Social Media Accounts

MSP4BIO’s audience represents a broad range of professional sectors, with a strong presence from **research (16 %)**, **education (13 %)**, **environmental services (19 %)** and **government administration (8 %)** (see Figure 10). Other key audiences include professionals in **Non-profit Organisations (7 %)**, **the blue economy (7.2 %)** and **consulting (3.7 %)**. Especially the prevalence of professionals from research, education and government administration showcases the success of the MSP4BIO’s dissemination and exploitation strategy, increasing the probability of uptake.

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Figure 12 MSP4BIO LinkedIn followers categorised by industry

Knowledge Transfer Using Social Media

The [MSP4BIO YouTube channel](#) served as a central hub for all **audiovisual content**, hosting a wide range of professionally produced videos, including webinar recordings, workshop sessions, and promotional materials (see Figure 13). These videos provided both an engaging and accessible window into the project's activities, offering immersive overviews of test sites, events, and scientific approaches. To maximise reach and impact, all videos were strategically promoted through the MSP4BIO website accompanied by blog posts and amplified via social media, driving traffic back to the platform and encouraging ongoing engagement with the project's results.

Highlight of the MSP4BIO's YouTube channel is the specially produced short documentary "[Cadiz Real Faces](#)" in the course of *D.4.1, Criteria for the representation for the social and economic dimension of MPAs*, which has become the most viewed video on the channel with **over 700 views**. This collaborative effort by the University of Cadiz (UCA) and [Mujeres del Mar](#) gives voice to local actors from the Bay of Cadiz, capturing their stories and perspectives on the cultural ecosystem services the bay provides. By exploring themes such as collective memory, cultural identity, and emotional ties to the marine landscape, the documentary offers a deeply human and locally grounded narrative emphasising the importance of integrating these values into sustainable spatial planning.

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Figure 13 Landing page of the MSP4BIO YouTube Channel with a preview of the Cadiz Real Faces documentary

3.4 Newsletter

In addition to its website and social media channels, MSP4BIO actively shared project insights, event promotions, and key updates through the **Blue Horizons Newsletter** — a joint communication initiative launched in September 2023 in partnership with its sister project, [Blue4All](#). This collaborative newsletter, currently reaching an audience of over **450 subscribers**, was designed to consolidate outreach efforts, streamline communication, and address a broader audience across projects. Designed to present a variety of information in a clear and cohesive format, each issue followed a consistent and purposeful structure:

1. Introduction
2. Joint update (when applicable)
3. MSP4BIO updates
4. BLUE4All updates
5. Upcoming events
6. External news (relevant for the audience on the topics shared above)
7. Announcements (such as Mission Ocean related news or opportunities)
8. Sister Projects Features
9. Publications

The value of this joint platform was further reinforced in late 2024, when the Blue Parks Mission Ocean project, [Blue Connect](#), joined the initiative. This expansion reflected a growing recognition of the importance of coordinated action and strategic alignment

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among marine conservation initiatives – an approach validated by strong engagement metrics, including an **average open rate exceeding 50%** and a **click rate of approximately 15%**. Together, the participating projects created a unified voice to amplify messages, promote knowledge exchange, and highlight synergies across projects. In parallel, MSP4BIO leveraged **targeted Flash Newsletters** — distributed specifically to the over **350 MSP4BIO subscribers** — to share time-sensitive updates, promote specific events, and deliver focused content such as invitations to the Blue Webinar Series. This multi-level communication approach ensured consistent engagement, offered frequent opportunities for stakeholder involvement, and fostered a strong sense of community among subscribers and partners (see Figure 12).

MSP4BIO has significantly outperformed its original goal of three newsletter publications with up to date **six Blue Horizons issues** and **two MSP4BIO Flash Newsletter Editions** (see Table 7):

09/2023 — [1st issue of the Blue Horizons Newsletter](#)

12/2023 — [2nd issue of the Blue Horizons Newsletter](#)

02/2024 — [3rd issue of the Blue Horizons Newsletter](#)

06/2024 — [4th issue of the Blue Horizons Newsletter](#)

12/2024 — [5th issue of the Blue Horizons Newsletter](#)

04/2025 — [6th issue of the Blue Horizons Newsletter](#)

05/2025 — [1st issue of the MSP4BIO Flash Newsletter](#)

06/2025 — [2nd issue of the MSP4BIO Flash Newsletter](#)

To maximise outreach and visibility, MSP4BIO was prominently featured in external newsletters such as the **SUBMARINER Network newsletter**, which currently reaches over **7,800 subscribers**. These appearances played a key role in broadening the audience for MSP4BIO's work and amplifying awareness of project objectives and ultimately leading to the project substantially exceeding its initial outreach goal of 500 newsletter subscribers (see Table 7 and Figure 14). By being showcased alongside other marine initiatives, the project strengthened its presence within the wider policy and research community, reinforcing the collaborative nature of efforts to protect marine biodiversity and promote sustainable ocean management.

MSP4BIO's internal communication was supported by the launch of a monthly/**bimonthly consortium newsletter**. This internal update provided concise progress summaries of Work Packages, links to publications and deliverables, next steps and upcoming events

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for project partners. It greatly facilitated coordination among partners, ensured alignment across workstreams, and offered an opportunity for team members to share their contributions and milestones. As a result, the internal newsletter not only kept the consortium well-informed but also strengthened team engagement and cohesion throughout the project.

Table 7 Overview of set KPI (Newsletter) and achievements

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	800 people reached	8,250 people reached
3 issues published	8 issues published	

(a)

(b)

Figure 14 Percentage of KPI of (a) people reached achieved and (b) issues released

3.5 Events and joint actions to maximise impact

3.5.1 Events

As a central pillar of its outreach strategy, MSP4BIO strategically leveraged events as platforms to communicate its project objectives, share key outcomes, and promote cross-sector collaboration. MSP4BIO has participated in **a total of 125 events**, actively participated in **over 50 conferences** and presented the MSP4BIO project in a total of **34 oral and poster presentations**. With these efforts, MSP4BIO was able to reach over **15,000 attendees** from diverse sectors including science, industry, policy and the general public (see Figure 15). The **scientific community** stood out as the most prominent one in the project’s outreach efforts, however also **industry** representatives and **policy makers** were reached throughout the project. Civil society and the general public were engaged through low-barrier events like the #Sailingtothefuture exhibition and [VLIZ’ Marine Science Day](#) in 2024. Besides eminent events hosted by MSP4BIO including Science-Policy Think Tanks and CoP interactions (see section 3.5.3 Project collaboration

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and stakeholder engagement), the project's outreach strategy further included the close cooperation with external events.

Figure 15 MSP4BIO Event metrics visualised

MSP4BIO was an active participant in the **Blue Mission Banos Mission Arenas** held in Gothenburg, Riga, Amsterdam and Sopot over the last three years. This project brought together hundreds of stakeholders including practitioners and experts from the Baltic and North Sea regions to discuss pathways to a carbon-neutral blue economy while incorporating innovative strategies for MPA governance and biodiversity protection. Furthermore, MSP4BIO complemented its outreach efforts with regular engagement in the **MED MSP Community of Practice (CoP)**, where project insights were actively disseminated and discussed. Notably, in June 2025, the project shared its final outcomes and the ESE Framework, sparking discussions on its legacy and relevance in the Mediterranean Sea basin. MSP4BIO also participated in high-level events such as **European Maritime Day** and **major MSP conferences**, engaging a broad range of stakeholders including representatives from the blue economy, public authorities, research institutions, and civil society. These occasions served to position the project within a wider network of EU-funded initiatives and policy dialogues, providing a platform to present its key outcomes and demonstrate their relevance to the implementation of recent European and regional marine, biodiversity, and spatial planning policies (see Figure 16).

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Check out MSP4BIO insights here:

Figure 16 Examples of external events MSP4BIO contributed to throughout the years with imbedded URLs to explore details.

The projects' efforts in event involvement have played a vital role in enhancing MSP4BIO's visibility, cooperation with other projects and initiatives, widen its stakeholder network and increasing the likelihood of uptake. Below you can find an extract of notable events MSP4BIO has hosted, contributed to or attended.

Table 8 MSP4BIO event highlights throughout the project's duration

Title Event	Date	Presentation or attendance	Partner involved
Steering Committee meeting of the EUSBRs Policy Area Spatial Planning	06/10/2022	Presentation	HELCOM
Future MARES 2nd Annual Meeting – session on synergies among HE marine projects	17/10/2022	Presentation briefly	SPRO
The final event of MAREA project	03/11/2022	Presentation	HELCOM
Marine Plan project Kick-off meeting	14/11/2022	Presentation	SPRO
MSP Global Forum , Barcelona	21/11/2022	Attendee	UAc
3rd International MSP Conference 2022 , Barcelona	22-23/11/2022	Presentation and booth	SPRO, CCMS, PAP/RAC, CEREMA

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I Jornada sobre el Espacio Litoral Marino de Canarias: Planificación y Gobernanza	25/11/2022	Presentation briefly	UAc
eMSP Project Workshop on Ecosystem-based management	02/12/2022	Presentation	HELCOM
EU Technical Expert Group on data for MSP	13/12/2022	Presentation	SPRO
BLUE4ALL kick-off meeting , Brussels	24-27/01/2023	Attendee	UTARTU, VLIZ, SPRO
Webinar: Maritime Spatial Planning in a changing climate	09/02/2023	Attendee	PAP/RAC
MPA Europe Kick-off meeting , Bodø	01/03/2023	Attendee	SPRO
International Congress on Sustainable Social Development and INDESS Workshop	15-17/03/2023	Presentation	UCA
ICZM & MSP workshop in the framework of the Transboundary CAMP Otranto project	11/05/2023	Presentation briefly	PAP/RAC
#OpenDoorsDay (Romania)	19/05/2023	Presentation briefly	NIMRD
Meeting of PAP/RAC Focal Points 2023	23-24/05/2023	Presentation	PAP/RAC
European Maritime Day 2023	24-25/05/2023	Presentation & booth	SPRO, CCMS, WWF
NatureNetwork Annual meeting	07-09/06/2023	Poster Presentation	SPRO
eMSP Workshop: Strengthening ecosystem-based approach in MSP and supporting sustainable blue economy	13-15/06/2023	Presented briefly	HELCOM
AESOP Conference 2023, Istanbul	11-15/07/2023	Presentation	GMU
ReMAP Project Meeting	08/08/2023	Presentation	UTARTU
Blue Mission BANOS Mission Arena 1 , Gothenburg	15/11/2023	Workshop	SPRO, UTARTU, HELCOM, WWF
2nd International Regina-MSP Workshop	06-08/02/2024	Workshop	UAc
Webinar: MED MSP CoP IV	13/02/2024	Presentation	CCMS, UAc
MSP4BIO Science-Policy Dialogue Think Tank	24/04/2024	Workshop	WWF MED, HELCOM, SYKE
Blue Mission BANOS Arena 2 , Riga	25-26/04/2024	Workshop	SYKE, HELCOM, SPRO
MED MSP CoP webinar: MSP4BIO Legacy	19/06/2025	Webinar	CNR, UAc, UCA, SPRO
Workshop: Climate-Ready Marine Protected Areas	10/12/2024	Presentation	CNR, SPRO
Blue Mission BANOS Arena 3 , Amsterdam	26-27/11/2024	Workshop	SPRO
European Ocean Days 2025, Brussels	3-7/03/2025	Presentation & booth	SPRO, CCMS

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Blue Mission BANOS Arena 4 , Sopot	28-30/04/2025	Presentation & booth	SPRO, GMU
36th European Cetacean Society Conference	25/04/2025	Workshop	UAc
Webinar: Advancing Marine Spatial Planning with Biodiversity Tools , Poland	14/05/2025	Workshop	GMU
European Maritime Days 2025, Cork	21-23/05/2025	Presentation & cross-project booth	SPRO, CCMS
Maritime Business Week Exhibition	20-23/05/2025	Presentation	NIMRD
One Ocean Science Congress 2025	3-6/06/2025	Poster Presentation	UCA
UN Ocean Conference 2025	9-13/06/2025	Presentation	SPRO, UAc
MPAinMSP Conference 2025	9-12/07/2025	Presentation	SPRO, CNR, UCA, UAc
MSP4BIO Final Policy Event , Brussels	23/06/2025	Workshop	SPRO, HELCOM, WWF Med
MSP4BIO Validation Workshop , Venice	2/07/2025	Workshop	All partners

Table 9 Overview of set KPIs (Events) and achievements

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	+20 Conferences attended	+50 attended so far
	+10 presentations given	34 presentations given
	+500 people attending presentations	15,000 people reached

3.5.2 Workshops & Webinars

MSP4BIO has recognised workshops and webinars as an indispensable measure for knowledge transfer and thus engaged in a wide range of events, with a strong focus on resource sharing and accessibility of project results. These events provided interactive spaces for stakeholders to engage directly with project tools, methods, and findings, fostering dialogue, feedback, and co-learning. By **connecting experts, policymakers, and practitioners across regions**, these formats helped translate complex scientific insights into actionable knowledge, ensuring relevance and real-world application. Highlights include the [final policy event co-hosted by CrossGov in June 2025](#), the [workshop at EMD 2023](#), the [ReginaMSP workshop 2024](#) and the [Blue Mission Banos Mission Arena Workshops](#). Up until today, the total number of knowledge-sharing sessions amounts to **over 70 events**, remarkably surpassing initially set KPIs, categorised in (see Table 10):

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- **Hosted:** +34 workshops and webinars were organised directly by the project – including Science-Policy Think Tanks, CoP interactions and other in-person and online workshops
- **Actively contributed:** MSP4BIO partners actively contributing to 28 external workshops and webinars in the form of oral or poster presentations, coaching or scientific expertise.
- **Attended:** MSP4BIO partners have attended at least 10 external workshops or webinar focusing on capacity building and knowledge exchange.

These efforts enabled partners to reach and interact with a targeted audience of **almost 2,000 stakeholders**, fostering meaningful discussions and in-depth exchanges across scientific, policy, and practitioner communities (see Figure 17).

Figure 17 MSP4BIO at events

A key component of its dissemination and exploitation strategy was the **MSP4BIO Blue Series** — a set of **five webinars close to the end of the project** designed to present key project outcomes in an interactive way. This webinar series was promoted using a coherent branding on social media accounts, as well as featured in different newsletters

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and incorporated in the integrated events calendar on the MSP4BIO website. By branding the sessions as a series, MSP4BIO ensured consistent framing and easier navigation for participants, helping the audience understand the progression of topics and avoid confusion. The series attracted **365 participants** from across the scientific community, policy institutions, industry, and the general public, further expanding the project's reach. To ensure long-term accessibility and knowledge transfer, all webinar recordings, were made available on the MSP4BIO YouTube channel and featured prominently on the project website through dedicated blog posts and social media promotion. This multi-platform approach supported both immediate engagement and lasting visibility for the project's outputs.

The MSP4BIO Blue Series

 [Nature-Inclusive Marine Spatial Planning: Insights from MSP4BIO Test Sites](#)
(09/04/2025)

 [MSP4BIO Webinar: Empowering Marine Spatial Planning with SeaSketch](#)
(17/05/2025)

 [MSP4BIO Webinar: Smart Tools for Preserved Seas: The MSP4BIO Ecological Toolkit and Real-World Applications](#) (28/05/2025)

 [MSP4BIO Webinar: How Can Marine Spatial Planning Help Achieve Europe's 30x30 Targets?](#) (06/06/2025)

 [MSP4BIO Webinar: Nature-Inclusive Approaches of the Blue Economy in MPAs](#)
(20/06/2025)

Validation Workshop

As part of the MSP4BIO Final Event from 2 to 4 July 2025 in Venice, a **dedicated validation workshop** was held – an essential milestone in ensuring the project's results were not only technically sound but also applicable in real-world planning contexts. By providing key stakeholders such as policy makers and project CoP members as well as sister projects with the opportunity to actively engage and respond to MSP4BIO's developed tools, policy guidance, and frameworks, the workshop ensured that final outputs were grounded in practical needs and perspectives. This participatory approach reinforced trust in MSP4BIO's contributions and positioned its legacy — from

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methodologies to knowledge platforms — as a lasting asset for ecosystem-based maritime spatial planning in Europe and beyond. Additional validation workshops were organised in three test sites – the **Baltic Sea**, **Romanian Black Sea coast**, and the **Bay of Cádiz** — generating site-specific feedback.

- In the **Baltic Sea**, final project results were presented by [HELCOM](#) to both the HELCOM MSP and Biodiversity Working Groups, while project coordinator s.Pro provided an overarching summary of outcomes.
- In **Romania**, MSP4BIO joined forces with the [BS-SEOS](#) project to host a high-impact workshop in Constanța, bringing together over 80 key stakeholders from governance, science, and industry. The event validated MSP4BIO outputs for the Western Black Sea, showcased smart monitoring tools, and highlighted synergies with complementary projects such as [FOCCUS EU](#), [Blue Connect](#), [SafeBless](#), and [ILIAD](#).
- The **Bay of Cádiz** hosted a dedicated roundtable where researchers from the University of the Azores and Universidad de Cádiz presented a “Roadmap for the Bay,” supported by a shared vision, institutional cooperation, and a co-creation programme linking governance, culture, and nature. The roundtable featured the proposal of a “Blue Bays Programme,” recognising semi-enclosed coastal areas—like Cádiz — as models of integrated governance.
- Additionally, a national webinar in **Poland** dedicated to the **Polish Maritime Administration**, showcased MSP4BIO tools and results and explored pathways for policy uptake: [MSP4BIO in Focus: Polish Webinar on Advancing Marine Spatial Planning with Biodiversity Tools](#) (14/05/2025)

Collectively, these events marked a crucial step in validating MSP4BIO’s outcomes, strengthening cross-sectoral engagement, and supporting future uptake at national, regional, and EU levels.

Table 10 Overview of set KPI (workshops) and achievements

	KPI set	KPI achieved
KPI check	3+ workshops/webinars	+70 workshops/webinars with 30+ hosted
	1 Validation Workshop	4 Validation Workshops

3.5.3 Project collaboration and stakeholder engagement

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Collaboration with sister and external projects in the fields of marine conservation and maritime spatial planning was a central pillar of MSP4BIO's outreach and impact strategy. Building strong relationships with complementary EU-funded initiatives played a pivotal role in amplifying the project's reach, strengthening its outputs, and ensuring long-term impact reaching diverse stakeholder groups across Europe and beyond. From the outset, close cooperation with **sister projects such as [Blue4All](#)** was a cornerstone in MSP4BIO's outreach strategy. These partnerships laid the foundation for collaborative communication efforts — most notably the launch of the **Blue Horizons Newsletter**, designed to streamline updates and maximise audience reach across aligned projects.

Further, MSP4BIO's **Science-Policy Think Tanks** evolved into a key corner stone in project collaboration, involving projects such as [MPAEUROPE](#), [eMSP](#), [REGINA MSP](#), [Blue4All](#), [REMAP](#), [MSPGREEN](#), [MARINE PLAN](#), [CROSSGOV](#), [Blue Connect](#), [NESBp](#) and [MEDIGREEN](#). These events not only enabled knowledge sharing and fostered active discussions but also resulted in the development of **joint policy recommendations** based on cross-project expertise. By building recommendations on a wide scientific expertise, these collectively supported messages substantially increase credibility and traction with policymakers and boost the potential for uptake (see section: Science-Policy Dialogue Think Tanks). These Science-Policy Think Tanks came to a close with a **final policy workshop held in Brussels** in June 2025, co-hosted by [CROSSGOV](#). The event strategically targeted policy uptake, amplifying key messages and ensuring that MSP4BIO's findings were contextualised within wider marine governance frameworks. The project's outreach extended to high-profile European initiatives such as **Blue Mission BANOS**, where MSP4BIO actively contributed to the **Mission Arenas** with interactive workshops showcasing tools and methodologies while embedding its work within the broader Mission Ocean narrative.

[MPA Community Network](#)

A notable legacy of MSP4BIO's cross-project engagement is the **MPA Community Network (MPA-CN)**, a collaborative platform launched in April 2025 through its' sister project [Blue4All](#). Designed to serve MPA managers and practitioners across Europe, the network brings together nine MPA related projects and promotes knowledge exchange as well as collaboration across the community. Starting in early 2026, the network will host MSP4BIO-developed tools on its *Tools and Blueprint* platform, ensuring continued access and use beyond the project's duration. The network also facilitated joint outreach activities, including the ["Design Your MPA Corridor" workshop](#) held at the **UN Ocean Conference 2025**, where conference attendees played the MPA Corridor Game, a co-developed efforts by the MPA-CN featuring tools and data directly derived from member projects (see Figure 18).

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The strength of partnerships established throughout the project was clearly demonstrated at **MSP4BIO’s Final Conference in Venice**, which brought together a broad spectrum of sister and external projects (see Figure 18). The active participation of initiatives such as [MPAEUROPE](#), [Blue4All](#), [REMAP](#), [MSPGREEN](#), [MARINE PLAN](#), [CROSSGOV](#), [Blue Connect](#), [NESBp](#), [MEDIGREEN](#), [BioAgora](#) and [BRIDGE-BS](#) in the validation workshop of the project reinforced MSP4BIO’s credibility and provided **valuable peer review** of its outputs. These collaborative ties not only amplified MSP4BIO’s impact but also laid the groundwork for a more cohesive and **coordinated European effort** in maritime spatial planning and biodiversity protection.

Figure 18 MSP4BIO Final Event in Venice, 2-4 July and the MPA Community Network at UNOC 2025.

Science-Policy Dialogue Think Tanks

A crucial mechanism for facilitating project collaboration was the development of Science-Policy Think Tanks, which emerged as a cornerstone of MSP4BIO’s engagement approach. **Four Science-Policy Dialogue Think Tanks** have been organised as part of Task 6.3, *Science-Policy Dialogues under multiple levels* between May 2023 and May 2025 (see Table 11). These meetings served as strategic arenas to foster **cross-project collaboration**, enhance policy dialogue and facilitate knowledge exchange on biodiversity mainstreaming into MSP. Their primary objective was to integrate diverse perspectives early in the project, ensuring that project tools, frameworks, and recommendations were shaped by **real-world needs and policy contexts**.

Table 11 Overview of the MSP4BIO Science-Policy Think Tanks

Think Tank	Date	Location	Participants
1st Think Tank	May 3, 2023	Online	34
2nd Think Tank	December 5, 2023	Online	20
3rd Think Tank	October 24, 2024	Marseille	26

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4th Think Tank	May 27, 2025	Online	17
Total			97

The four Think Tank meetings brought together a total of **97 participants**, including **11 EU-funded projects** and initiatives representatives - [MPAEUROPE](#), [eMSP](#), [REGINA MSP](#), [Blue4All](#), [REMAP](#), [MSPGREEN](#), [MARINE PLAN](#), [CROSSGOV](#), [BLUECONNECT](#), [NESBp](#) and [MEDIGREEN](#). Notable policy stakeholders contributed throughout the process, including representatives from **DG MARE** and **DG ENVIRONMENT**, who offered insights on directive implementation and policy coherence strategies within EU planning and conservation frameworks.

The first meeting laid the groundwork for cross-project coordination and initiated the classification of tools and outcomes relevant to biodiversity mainstreaming. The second meeting deepened policy engagement by identifying systemic barriers to directive alignment, particularly between the MSFD and MSPD, and discussing mechanisms to improve coherence across frameworks. The third meeting focused on refining the policy recommendations developed in Deliverable D6.2, integrating stakeholder and EU representatives feedback and identifying opportunities for operationalization. The final Think Tank consolidated inputs into a shared set of policy recommendations and initiated the development of a **Joint Policy Brief** that synthesises contributions from participating projects. It also contributed to a broader understanding of the thematic and operational landscape of projects, by informing a classification of main tools and outcomes and revealing thematic clusters and synergies between initiatives.

Some of the key highlights of the Think Tank meetings include:

- **A broad and Diverse Participation:** The meetings gathered a wide range of stakeholders, including project partners, EU representatives (DG MARE, DG ENV), conservation and planning experts.
- **A collaborative Mapping and Synergy Analysis:** Participants feedback informed the mapping of project tools and outcomes, and the potential synergies among them. This process was acknowledged as a valuable step towards enhancing the collective understanding of available resources.
- **Joint Policy Recommendations:** The Think Tank series culminated in the development of a shared policy communication tool—the *Joint Policy Brief on Policy Recommendations*. This document synthesizes common priorities and solutions for policy coherence and facilitates knowledge transfer across governance levels and sea basins. Seven initiatives contributed to this coordinated effort, promoting greater policy coherence and alignment.

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To bring the Science-Policy Think Tanks to a meaningful close, a final cross-project session was held during the MSP4BIO final event, amounting to a total of **5 Think Tanks**. By involving decision-makers and practitioners in co-creation processes, the Think Tanks significantly enhanced the relevance, applicability, and potential uptake of MSP4BIO's results. Moreover, they provided a valuable forum for aligning efforts across projects, identifying synergies, and building a shared understanding of challenges and solutions in MSP and biodiversity protection. This collaborative model not only strengthened MSP4BIO's visibility but also helped lay the foundation for lasting partnerships and continued knowledge exchange beyond the project's duration.

Further information is available in the following reports and post:

- [1st Think Tank Report can be checked out here](#)
- [2nd Think Tank Report can be checked out here](#)
- [3rd Think Tank Report can be checked out here](#)
- [4th Think Tank Report can be checked out here](#)

CoP Interactions

Communities of Practices (CoPs) were established early on in the project to support project implementation and amplify applicability of project outcomes by striving for a participatory approach in all test sites. The uptake of MSP4BIO outcomes such as the ESE Framework across its test sites highlights both their practical value for MSP and MPA processes and the effectiveness of the project's dissemination and exploitation strategy, with **CoPs playing a key role in ensuring local recognition and support**. CoPs helped guarantee that solutions were not only scientifically sound but also aligned with real policy processes and stakeholder priorities — creating fertile ground for dissemination and long-term impact by

- **Co-creation and validation of project tools and outcomes:** CoPs were established very early in the project involving key site-specific stakeholders. Through 5 interactions CoP members were involved in co-creation of the main management questions, co-creation and testing of project tools, and co-creation and validation of ESE framework applications creating site specific solutions.
- **Increased Awareness:** CoP interactions supported awareness efforts and build capacity among practitioners, laying the groundwork for future uptake.

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- **Knowledge transfer:** CoPs enabled knowledge transfer to relevant authorities and contributed to the continuity of this work beyond the project’s lifetime.
- **Policy Relevance:** CoPs facilitated engagement with broader regional bodies, such as the Black Sea Commission, reinforcing dissemination across governance levels.

CoPs served not only as vehicles for stakeholder participation but as **critical instruments for dissemination and legacy** across all test sites, ensuring that MSP4BIO’s tools, knowledge, and results continue to inform marine planners and practitioners well beyond the project’s lifetime. Originally aiming for at least two CoP interactions per test site, the project significantly exceeded this target by holding **up to five interactive CoP events at each site with a total of 340 attendees combined** (see Table 12). Please refer to D5.5, *Report on participatory process in test sites* (Alloncle *et al.*, 2025) for more insights. This strong level of engagement reflects MSP4BIO’s clear commitment to local collaboration, ensuring that project results were not only validated by stakeholders but also positioned for real-world uptake and long-term impact.

Table 12 Overview of KPI’s (stakeholder engagement) and achievements

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	2+ Policy Think Tanks	5 Think Tanks
	+5 science-policy interactions	11 Collaborations
	2+ CoP interaction per test site	Up to 5 interactions per site

3.7 External featuring and Media outreach

A wide range of project partners, platforms, and related initiatives focused on MSP and MPAs played a significant role in amplifying MSP4BIO’s messages and promoting the project more broadly (see Figure 19). Throughout its duration, MSP4BIO gained visibility through external channels — not only via reposts, comments, and likes, but also through original posts and prominent features on their platforms.

Social media outreach was significantly boosted by initiatives with large and engaged audiences, including [HELCOM](#), [WWF Med](#), [Mission Ocean](#), [CINEA](#), [REA \(European Research Executive Agency\)](#), [PAP/RAC](#), [CNR-ISMAR](#), [s.Pro](#), [SUBMARINER Network](#), [EU MSP Platform](#), the [Blueeconomyhub](#) and the [MSP Global Initiative](#). In addition, sister and related projects such as [Blue4All](#), [Blue Connect](#) and [MPA Europe](#) actively supported the dissemination of MSP4BIO content. These combined efforts contributed to an

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increase of **over 250,000 people reached** through social media, marking a major success in the project's outreach strategy.

External platforms also played a vital role in visibility. MSP4BIO partners significantly supported media outreach by publishing distinct news pieces about the project on their institutional websites with **at least 34 articles** published today (e.g. [CCMS – Start of the MSP4BIO project](#) and [CNR-ISMAR](#)). The co-produced documentary *Cadiz Real Faces*, hosted on the MSP4BIO YouTube channel, was featured on two locally relevant websites ([University of Cádiz](#) and [Mujeres del Mar](#)), extending its reach and visibility through trusted regional platforms. A variety of established **European and regional platforms and initiatives** further disseminated MSP4BIO insights, upcoming events and milestones demonstrating the project's recognition within established marine and policy communication channels such as [the Horizon Europe Work programme 2023-25](#), [EMODnet](#), [EU Aquaculture Assistance Mechanism](#), the [EU MSP Platform](#), [CINEA](#), the [SUBMARINER Network](#), [CrossGov](#), [HELCOM](#), [PAP/RAC](#), [CCMS](#) and [the MPA Community Network](#). These efforts led to an **additional estimated reach of over 250,000 people**.

Figure 19 Visualisation of external outreach supporting MSP4BIO

3.7.1 Press releases

Media outreach made a notable contribution in increasing the visibility and impact of the MSP4BIO project on a **regional level**, complementing its core dissemination strategy and helping to engage wider audiences beyond the scientific and policy-making communities.

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MSP4BIO actively pursued collaboration with external media channels through press releases, interviews, and multimedia content. As a result, the project was featured in **at least 8 distinct articles** across newspapers and other relevant forums including the [Jornal Correio dos Açores](#), the [Estonian Science News Portal Novaator](#) and the [Romanian Ministry of Research, Innovation and Digitalization Newsletter](#) (see Figure 20). **Two interviews** about the project were published in Azorean newspapers, ensuring that regional voices and perspectives were reflected and heard locally. Altogether, these media engagements significantly strengthened MSP4BIO's public profile and helped position the project as a reference point in the evolving discourse on marine biodiversity and spatial planning. **WWF Med** is preparing a **final press release** to highlight the project's outcomes, with a particular focus on the joint policy recommendations developed through the Science-Policy Think Tanks.

Table 13 Overview of KPI's (press releases) and achievements

KPI check	KPI set	KPI achieved
	+6 press releases and articles	8 press releases 1 in preparation

Figure 20 MSP4BIO featured in press and newspaper articles

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3.8 Dialogue and feedback loops

To ensure responsive and adaptive stakeholder engagement, MSP4BIO implemented a series of targeted surveys throughout the project’s lifespan to gather structured feedback and refine its approaches. **Two dedicated questionnaires** were developed and distributed in 2024 and 2025 to collect stakeholder impressions on the Community of Practice (CoP) interactions. The first survey included 15 questions and was translated to the native language of each region to encourage accessibility and inclusiveness. The second, distributed in 2025, consisted of 13 questions aimed at capturing final reflections on the CoP process. The feedback collected through these surveys was systematically analysed and integrated into the project’s engagement strategy to improve and optimise CoP activities. Summary infographics illustrating key findings are presented in Figure 21. Please refer to Annex A and B for a detailed overview. This feedback loop played a vital role in enhancing the quality and relevance of interactions across test sites. In addition, **one separate survey** was launched and open during the MSP4BIO Final Event (2–4 July 2025) to maintain open and transparent dialogue with participants. While no responses were received for this particular survey, the initiative reflects the project's ongoing commitment to stakeholder inclusivity and continuous learning.

Figure 21 Summary infographics on feedback for CoP interactions 2024 & 2025

3.9 Reflections and future improvements

1. Reflections on Communication and Dissemination Achievements

- **Effective multi-channel outreach:** MSP4BIO successfully utilised a range of communication channels — including newsletters, social media, webinars, and workshops — to reach its diverse target audiences. The project website served as a central hub for updates, publications, and resources, contributing to open science, FAIR data (see D1.4 Final Data Management Plan), accessibility and transparency.
- **Tailored engagement for key audiences:** Dedicated efforts were made to tailor messaging for different stakeholder groups, from EU-level policymakers and national authorities to researchers and NGOs. This was reflected in the clear language used in policy briefs and the visual storytelling approaches in infographics and video content.
- **Strong cross-project synergies:** Coordinated dissemination efforts with related EU projects (e.g. Blue4All, MPA Europe, Blue Connect, ULTFARMS, MSP-GREEN, eMSP NBSR etc) were ensured for joint messaging and mutual amplification.
- **Collaborative dissemination via partners:** Leveraging the networks of project partners and associated initiatives (e.g. MSP Platform, MPA Community Network, MSP4BIO Think tanks etc) increased the project's visibility. Participation in key European events (e.g. European Maritime Day, Mission Ocean events, MPA/MSP conferences) also enhanced outreach.
- **Interactive and participatory tools:** The use of interactive webinars, co-creation sessions, story maps and knowledge exchange platforms fostered two-way communication and stakeholder ownership.

2. Challenges and Areas for Improvement

- **Limited reach beyond core stakeholders:** Despite strong engagement within the biodiversity conservation, MSP communities, broader outreach to less-involved sectors (e.g. blue economy sectors, such as renewables, nonliving resources) remained limited. Future projects could benefit from a more industry-specific communication plan.
- **Language and accessibility barriers:** Most materials were produced in English, which may have limited accessibility for some regional or local actors. Translating key outputs or offering summaries in multiple languages could expand impact.

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- **Monitoring impact and feedback:** While dissemination outputs were tracked, systematic evaluation of impact (e.g. how materials were used, who engaged most effectively, what influenced policy) was limited. More robust tracking and feedback mechanisms (e.g. surveys, analytics, user interviews) would strengthen future efforts.
- **Further invest in evaluation and adaptation:** Include structured evaluation of communication impact and integrate learning loops to adjust strategies in real-time during the project lifecycle.

3.10 Overall Outreach Impact

Throughout its duration, MSP4BIO achieved broad and impactful outreach across multiple channels, surpassing initial KPIs and securing strong visibility for its outcomes (see Figure 22). The project website became a central information hub, hosting **65 blog posts** and attracting **over 35,000 visits** and **12,000 unique clicks** — thanks to an engaging, cohesive design and effective social media redirection. Visitors engaged deeply with the site, making the publications section one of the top three most viewed pages. Social media was a key asset for this success. While MSP4BIO began with a presence on several platforms — including X (formerly Twitter), YouTube, LinkedIn, and BlueBioMatch — LinkedIn emerged as the most prominent communication channel. The platform gained **over 800 followers**, saw more than **300 reposts** of project content, and consistently reached professionals in research, education, and government administration —MSP4BIO's core target audiences. This strategic focus not only supported high engagement but also enhanced the potential for policy and institutional uptake. YouTube complemented this effort as a **repository** for webinars, workshops, and multimedia storytelling, most notably the documentary "*Cadiz Real Faces*", which was viewed over 600 times and featured on external platforms. The jointly produced **Blue Horizons Newsletter** — with sister projects Blue4All and Blue Connect — and external newsletters further extended the project's reach, engaging over **8,000 readers**.

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MSP4BIO KPI Check - Outreach

Figure 22 Overall MSP4BIO KPI overview and achievements

MSP4BIO’s physical and virtual presence in **over 120 events** — including **53 conferences** and **more than 70 workshops/webinars** — enabled knowledge transfer and interactive dialogue with **over 15,000 participants**. The **Science-Policy Think Tanks**, the final policy event in Brussels, and the validation workshop in Venice were especially influential in driving the policy relevance of MSP4BIO outputs, fostering cross-project collaboration and deep engagement with policymakers. Synergies with related initiatives were established early in the project and continuously strengthened over time, enhancing both the quality of MSP4BIO’s outputs and its strategic visibility. These collaborations significantly expanded the project’s outreach potential, with extensive external featuring and media engagement contributing to a total audience of **640,000 people** (see Figure 23). As of today, **eight dedicated press releases** were published discussing the project and high-profile platforms — including the **EU MSP Platform, BlueEconomyHub, CINEA, REA, Mission Ocean, WWF Med, HELCOM, the SUBMARINER Network, and MPA Europe** — played a key role in amplifying MSP4BIO’s messages and ensuring broad dissemination across the marine and policy communities.

The project successfully engaged a wide range of stakeholders, particularly from science, education, and environmental services. While engagement with the private sector remained limited, targeted efforts through CoPs allowed for meaningful dialogue with regional and sectoral actors. Overall, MSP4BIO’s dissemination and communication activities laid a strong foundation for lasting impact. With several steps already taken toward exploitation and legacy-building – including **three policy briefs, 13 factsheets**

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and **+10 scientific publications** developed in MSP4BIO – the project is well positioned to feed into key policy processes such as the upcoming revision of the MSPD and MSFD.

Figure 23 Visualisation of MSP4BIO's overall outreach impact

4. Exploitation Roadmap

Building on the MSP4BIO Final Dissemination Report, which documented the communication and outreach activities carried out during the project, this Exploitation Roadmap focuses on ensuring the continued use and impact of MSP4BIO's tools, knowledge, and recommendations. It outlines how project outcomes can be adopted, adapted, and scaled by planners, MPA managers, authorities, and stakeholders to support biodiversity integration into Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) across Europe and beyond. The roadmap also identifies pathways for long-term uptake and emphasizes the importance of sustained cross-sectoral cooperation and governance coherence.

4.1 Key Exploitable Results

The MSP4BIO project has produced several important outputs that are ready for exploitation.

The **Integrated Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) Management Framework** is the main outcome of MSP4BIO project, available as a document format and as an online platform (<https://msp4bio.eu/ese-management-framework/>). It represents a holistic conceptual framework designed to support decision-makers in integrating biodiversity conservation with economic and social aspects in MSP.

In addition to the ESE Framework, its modules – building components are among the KERs:

- 1) **ESE module 1 - Ecological Toolkit²**: MSP4BIO has improved existing and created a new practical, adaptable set of decision-supporting tools and methodologies, designed to support national and regional MSP and MPA authorities. These tools were applied in MSP4BIO test sites, producing site-specific solutions contributing to future and ongoing MSP and MPA processes. The Ecological Toolkit integrates:

1.1 Portfolio of improved ecological criteria to be applied in systemic biodiversity protection and restoration: The MSP4BIO portfolio of improved ecological criteria for systemic biodiversity protection and restoration offers a scientifically grounded set of indicators to evaluate and prioritise marine areas for protection, based on ecological value, connectivity, resilience, and vulnerability. It is designed to support marine spatial planners, MPA managers, and policymakers in making more informed, transparent, and biodiversity-aligned spatial decisions.

1.2 Guidance for building climate change scenarios for protection strategies: The MSP4BIO Climate-Smart MPAs Guidance offers tools to incorporate climate

² Deliverable 3.4 Ecological toolkit (ESE 1) for MPAs prioritization and networking

change in biodiversity and planning strategies and provides a structured approach for integrating climate change scenarios into the design, planning, and management of marine protected areas. It supports planners and conservation authorities in making MPAs more adaptive and resilient by anticipating climate-driven shifts in species, habitats, and ecosystem dynamics.

- 2) **ESE module 2 - Socio-economic and governance criteria and indicators³**: A refined set of socio-economic criteria and indicators developed and validated through test site applications. These enable planners and policymakers to understand and balance biodiversity objectives with social and economic needs. The criteria contribute to transparent trade-off analysis and support more equitable decision-making in MSP processes.
- 3) **ESE module 3 - Participatory development of integrated trade-off scenarios⁴. Good management practices for blue economy sectors⁵**, such as fisheries, tourism, aquaculture, mineral extraction and energy development.
- 4) **Policy coherence solutions⁶**: Aimed at strengthening MSPs' compatibility with the new biodiversity policy requirements. These evidence-based proposals were discussed with decision- and policymakers at different levels (national, regional, EU) to support better policy coherence at different levels, and integration of biodiversity targets within related EU and national processes and related policy instruments.
- 5) **MPA/MSP strategic integration framework⁷**: Presents MSP4BIO MPA/MSP integration model and establishes a systematic approach to integrating MPAs into MSP across three phases: preplanning, planning, and implementation.

³ Deliverable 4.1 Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs

⁴ Deliverable 4.3 Trade-offs method for protection and restoration in MSP – ESE3

⁵ Guideline for the strategic and spatial measures for the nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors - ESE3

⁶ Deliverable 6.2 Future directions for the EU, regional seas and national implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy in the coastal and marine regions

⁷ Deliverable 4.4 Strategic Guidance on the integration of MPA and MSP on multiple governance and ecosystem levels

Figure 24 ESE framework conceptual model – ESE modules.

In addition, the ESE Framework integrates the following KERs:

6 demonstrators at different governance levels - Test site solutions and lessons learned⁸: Demonstrations from real-world marine and coastal areas representing 5 EU sea-basins provide insights into implementing the ESE framework in varied ecological, governance, and policy contexts producing site specific solutions. It includes results of the cross-test site analysis and recommendations on the transferability of results and potentials for its upscaling.

EU-wide overview of biodiversity data availability & knowledge gaps inventory⁹: A structured inventory of biodiversity-related data (including criteria) for proper implementation of tools and methodologies and better integration of biodiversity in spatial planning. This includes an MSP4BIO database app prepared to quickly and easily view and filter the datasets, data platforms, and tools that were compiled.

The project produced, in addition:

⁸ Deliverables 5.3 and 5.4: Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration and Final recommendations, transferability and scale-up of effective biodiversity mainstreaming in MSP

⁹ Deliverable 2.1 Overview of the available biodiversity datasets and platforms relevant for planning and <https://msp4bio.vliz.be/>

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Stakeholder engagement strategies¹⁰: Documented methods for organising and implementing Communities of Practice for small, very local sites, as well as larger transboundary and sea-basin areas, ensuring inclusive, multi-actor participation in MPA/MSP processes.

Key barriers and levers for policy coherence¹¹: Detailed analysis available at the EU, regional and national levels.

Policy briefs¹²: Final project policy brief and joint policy recommendations among sister and related projects.

Training modules & communication materials: Targeted learning, dissemination and awareness tools to support capacity building across stakeholder groups.

More detailed information on the exploitation of each of these results is available in the chapter 4.6.

4.2 Target users and stakeholders

Target Stakeholders & End-Users

Key groups expected to exploit the results include:

- **EU Institutions (e.g., DG MARE, DG ENV):** Use of MSP4BIO outputs to inform policy updates, specifically the implementation of the EU Ocean Pact and announced review and revision of MSFD and MSP Directives, as well as the EU Biodiversity Strategy tracking.
- **National and regional MSP authorities:** Integration of the ESE framework tools and test site application results into current and upcoming MSP plans updates and revisions, as well for conservation planning and MPAs management processes.
- **Environmental authorities and MPA Managers:** Integration of the ESE framework application results into MPA designations/expansion/strict protection.
- **Regional Sea Conventions (e.g., HELCOM, OSPAR, Barcelona convention, Black Sea Convention):** Use of ESE assessment methods, policy solutions, and

¹⁰ Deliverables 5.2 Test sites methodology including the participation strategy and 5.5 Report on the participatory process in test sites

¹¹ State of the art on key barriers and levers for policy coherence

¹² Deliverables 6.4 Joint policy recommendations and 7.5 Policy Brief

test site strategic and spatial solutions to strengthen regional coordination and implementation of conservation and planning goals, as well as to fill in the gaps in the implementation of relevant regional strategies and initiatives related to marine planning and achievement of biodiversity goals.

- **NGOs and Civil society organisations:** MSP4BIO built upon technical assessments provided by NGOs proposing recommendations for better alignment between MPA and MSP processes. There is significant potential in utilizing MSP4BIO results, evidence, and tools for ongoing advocacy and policy engagement. .
- **Researchers and research institutions:** Use MSP4BIO toolkits and solutions to further advance their research on Cumulative Impacts, Strategic Environmental Assessments, ecosystem-based MSP, and science-based, biodiversity-smart/climate smart MSP and MPAs.
- **Research projects & networks (e.g., Mission Ocean, BioAgora, Blue Parks, Blue Connect, MPA Community Network, new projects):** Building on MSP4BIO's methodologies, tools and solutions, especially in cumulative impact assessments, ecological connectivity and spatial assessments, as well as identified policy coherence barriers and suggested policy recommendations. Continue populating the MSP4BIO ESE Framework with management questions, answers, application examples etc.
- **Universities and training providers:** Adoption of educational resources and toolkits to enrich MSP and MPA-related curricula.
- **Private sector and blue economy clusters:** Use of MSP4BIO's spatial data protocols and biodiversity indicators to evaluate sustainable investment decisions. Use good management practices for 5 blue economy sectors (fisheries, aquaculture, renewables, extraction of marine non-living resources, tourism) offered by MSP4BIO for nature-inclusive design of blue economy sectors to guide the operationalisation of their work.

4.3 Exploitation strategies for wide uptake (scientific, policy, open source)

MSP4BIO's exploitation strategy is based on three parallel channels:

- **Open source & practitioner access:** All tools, indicators, and protocols are and will be hosted under open-access licenses on the [MSP4BIO website](#), EU MSP

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Platform, and repositories like Zenodo ([MSP4BIO Community](#)) to ensure maximum long-term accessibility and adaptability. MSP4BIO reports and publications will be as well integrated into SUBMARINER Network website and the MPA Community Network, specifically in its Toolbox section (<https://mpacommunity.network/msp4bio/>). Connected modelling tools suggested in the Ecological Toolkit and used for the site-specific solutions are hosted by their original hosting services, which are open-access and available for use. Webinars/capacity building materials (videos), as well as guidance documents are available on MSP4BIO website.

- **Scientific Uptake:** Peer-reviewed open access articles, technical reports, and conference contributions, as well as easily accessible project outcomes on different platforms, ensure integration into marine conservation science and spatial planning research. Publications are already available on MSP4BIO website (see Figure 5 MSP4BIO publication section showing the scientific publication carousel with previews of this document). The ESE Framework and Toolkit are being and will be promoted via academic networks of research/academia project partners (please see subchapter 4.6).
- **Policy Uptake:** The project delivers targeted briefs and webinars to inform the ongoing implementation of the EU Ocean pact, review of the EU MSFD and MSP Directives, regional and national biodiversity protection and marine planning implementation processes and the implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy. MSP4BIO policy solutions can support national policy dialogues on direct marine conservation integration into MSP reviews and updates. Science-Policy dialogues cross-project Think tanks provide joint recommendations produced in synergy and validated by different related projects working on MPAs or MSP.

4.4 Key Actors, Timelines, and Milestones for Biodiversity Integration in Marine Decision-Making

Achieving long-term biodiversity integration in Maritime Spatial Planning requires coordinated efforts of both public and private actors, underpinned by clear timelines and measurable milestones. Building on MSP4BIO's outcomes and communication and dissemination efforts, with continued wide promotion of briefs/factsheets/promo materials prepared for all KERs of MSP4BIO project, the following roadmap identifies priority actions for various stakeholder groups. For each group, details on actions that already

took place during project implementations are provided, as well as envisaged/suggested activities to take place in the period 0-36 months after the project end.

For more details on the outreach of MSP4BIO project to key actors, please see chapter 3.5 Events and joint actions to maximise impact, which shows that MSP4BIO was able to reach through events an audience of over 15,000 attendees from diverse sectors including science, industry, policy and the general public (Figure 15).

A. Public sector actors

European institutions (DG MARE, DG ENV, EEA, JRC)

- **During project implementation:** Participation of relevant EU DGs in MSP4BIO Science-Policy dialogues and policy-related discussions and events (such as MSP Conference, EMD workshops), as well as participation/attendance in MSP4BIO webinars, CrossGov/MSP4BIO projects Joint Policy Day, as well as MSP4BIO Final event.
- **Milestone (0–6 months):** Reflect MSP4BIO recommendations in the ongoing review of MSFD and implementation of the Ocean Pact, and implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy at national/regional/local levels and its future updates. Promote harmonised biodiversity indicators and ESE framework adoption via EU platforms (e.g., EMODnet, MSP Assistance Mechanism, which will receive final MSP4BIO outcomes upon approval).
- **Milestone (6–18 months):** Same as above. Build upon relevant MSP4BIO results during the process of the Ocean Act preparation, as well as in any other upcoming sectoral update.
- **Milestone (18–36 months):** Incorporate MSP4BIO results in the upcoming review of MSP Directive, in particular, policy coherence solutions and joint policy recommendations.

National and regional MSP authorities

- **During project implementation:** Participation of national and regional actors in MSP4BIO Science-Policy discussions and CoP interactions, as well as in the tailored webinars organised with the MED MSP CoP, HELCOM VASAB MSP and Biodiversity WGs, and in the Black Sea cross-project events. National and local authorities have been directly involved in the Communities of Practice in the test sites, participating in tools demonstrations, validation and co-creation of site-specific solutions through ESE applications. Specific final validation events

organised in Spain (Cadiz), Poland (Sopot), Romania, as well as at the Final project event (see Dissemination report).

- **Milestone (0–6 months):** Get familiar with the guidance documents and training materials. Pay attention in particular to MPA/MSP integration framework/model and underlying country level assessments.
- **Milestone (6–18 months):** Start using MSP4BIO tools in ongoing MPA and MSP frameworks and processes and ensure trainings on using ESE Framework. Pilot the ESE Framework/tools application in further MPA/MSP processes in line with the interested management questions, such as in Italy.
- **Milestone (18–36 months):** Same as the previous point. Embed biodiversity targets and socio-ecological indicators in national MSP regulations and guidance documents, depending on the stage of national MSP processes.

Regional Sea Conventions (e.g. HELCOM, OSPAR, Barcelona convention, Black Sea Convention)

- **During project implementation:** Direct participation of HELCOM (Helsinki Convention – Baltic Sea), representatives of the Black Sea Convention and PAP/RAC (UNEP MAP – Barcelona Convention, Mediterranean Sea) in the project implementation, with important roles in the policy work. The Black Sea Convention representatives participated in the Black Sea CoP interactions, especially for validation of ESE and DSTs for planning solution, and in dedicated cross project meetings (see dissemination report), while the Project was presented to the MSP Working Group of Barcelona Convention.
- **Milestone (6–18 months):** Further incorporate MSP4BIO tools and policy solutions in joint regional assessments and action plans.
- **Milestone (6–18 months):** Align basin-scale targets and activities with policy recommendations.

B. Private sector actors

Blue economy clusters & SMEs

- **During project implementation:** Participation in some of the CoP interactions, such as in Cadiz, Azores, and in the Black Sea (the Black Sea Economic Cooperation Organization). Targeted webinar organised dedicated to discussions on the nature-inclusive design of blue economy sectors. Project results promoted in events dedicated to nature restoration and ocean multi-use.

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- **Milestone (0–6 months):** Access MSP4BIO guidance and methodologies/fact sheets and training materials for uptake of recommendations on the nature-inclusive operations of sectors.
- **Milestone (6–18 months):** Collaborate with planners and environmental agencies in local/regional MSP co-creation participatory trade-off scenario development processes.
- **Milestone (18–36 months):** Demonstrate biodiversity-smart business models in aquaculture, ecotourism, or fisheries, through upcoming projects (e.g. new Ocean Mission Blue Parks project on strict protection).

Marine infrastructure developers (e.g., Wind, Ports, Cables)

- **Milestone (0–6 months):** Participate in knowledge exchange forums to understand biodiversity-inclusive planning.
- **Milestone (6–24 months):** Integrate ESE criteria into Environmental Impact Assessments (EIAs) and investment planning, through the ongoing projects on minimisation of impacts of offshore wind energy.

C. Cross-cutting support actions

Academia & research institutes

- **Ongoing:** Direct work of researchers across different sea basins in MSP4BIO project. High number of publications resulting from the projects (11), contributing to manuscripts, presentation on numerous events (127). Further work on MSP4BIO approaches, their reuse, uptake and upgrade.

Civil society & NGOs

- **Ongoing:** Direct engagement during project implementation in CoPs in the test sites and participation in the co-creation and validation processes. WWF MED and WWF EPO direct participation in MSP4BIO results – promote MSP4BIO's tools in their networks and important WGs such as the EU MSP Expert WG.

Training and capacity providers

- **Milestone (0–18 months):** Embed MSP4BIO content into marine governance curricula and professional development.
- **Milestone (ongoing-24):** Publish and track the impact of the Massive Open Online Course Module on MPA/MSP including contributions from MSP4BIO project

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(ongoing work by SUBMARINER Network/s.Pro, in cooperation with BlueBioTechnepreuners project).

By aligning these actor-specific actions with realistic timelines and milestones, MSP4BIO's exploitation strategy moves from tool deployment to systemic transformation—ensuring that biodiversity is a foundational criterion in both policy and investment decisions affecting Europe's seas.

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4.5 Action Plan and timeline

Table 14 Phased Exploitation Timeline

Period	Key Actions
<p>Final months of the project–6 months post-project</p>	Disseminate final reports, briefs and recorded webinars
	Host policy-focused final event (co-organised with CrossGov, on 23 June 2025, in Brussels)
	Publish peer-reviewed outputs
	Transfer ESE Framework and all-important outputs to MSP Platform, Zenodo, Nature Network Community
	Final presentation of project results, ESE Framework including policy recommendations to the EU DGs, experts, related projects, MSP and MPA practitioners, policy and decision makers at the MSP4BIO Final event and during the final review meeting (EU policy makers)
	Contributions to international biodiversity and MSP dialogues (e.g., MPA in MSP International Conference in Bodo, UN Ocean Conference, valid also for the longer-term plans)
<p>6–18 months</p>	Integrate MSP4BIO final results into MPA Community Network website (planned launch of the draft website beginning of 2026)
	Participate in national and regional capacity-building workshops organised by MSP4BIO participating institutions, in synergy with other ongoing projects/initiatives
	Presentation in the cross-projects joint session at 2026 World Biodiversity Conference
	Use of ESE Framework and its tools by national/regional MSP practitioners, made available and presented to regional WGs and CoPs during project implementation (MED MSP CoP, Black Sea Commission and Black Sea Economic Cooperation Organization, HELCOM VASAB MSP and HELCOM Biodiversity WG)
	Support MSFD revision and implementation of the EU Ocean Pact

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	Development of follow-up proposals through Interreg, LIFE, or Mission Ocean calls
	Use of MSP4BIO outcomes in ongoing/upcoming related projects such as NESBp, MEDIGREEN, Blue Connect , Blue4All , BioAgora (all cooperations already established)
18–36 months	Form partnerships for new Horizon/IEU funded proposals
	Integration of tools and methods into national MSP review cycles - continuous
	Conduct analysis of the implementation of this exploitation strategy and adjust exploitation efforts if needed
	Maintain ESE website as part of CNR workstreams. SUBMARINER/s.Pro will maintain the MPA CN website long term. Maintain MSP4BIO website (continuous, for at least 5 years; to be further maintained through the MPA CN website).

4.6 Exploitation plan for MSP4BIO Key Exploitable Results

The exploitation plan for the MSP4BIO Key Exploitable Results are detailed in the section below. For each deliverable, both the exploitation at project level and per partner is outlined below.

Exploitable Result 1: D2.1 - Overview of the available biodiversity datasets and platforms relevant for planning
Description of result
Inventory of existing marine biodiversity datasets and platforms applicable to MSP and MPA processes.
Project exploitation route
Open access database and document available open access (MSP4BIO website) early in the project implementation. Wide dissemination through social media, events, project presentation, sharing with sister and other relevant projects and initiatives. A dedicated factsheet prepared for easier dissemination.

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Post-project: Integrate into national MSP and MPA processes and relevant EU projects, shared through knowledge hubs and data portals (e.g., Zenodo, EMODnet).
Target groups
MSP planners, MPA managers, marine scientists, data managers, authorities.
Sector of application
MPA/MSP, Marine data management.
Impact
Facilitates evidence-based marine conservation and spatial planning and supports overcoming data gaps across the EU.
IPR measures
Open-access compilation; licensing depends on original datasets.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Varying data standards and access rights; mitigated by interoperability guidelines.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
s.Pro/VLIZ: Make sure that the database: https://msp4bio.vliz.be/ is available in Zenodo, MPA CN, MSP4BIO website.
All partners: share within new projects working on MPA/MSP/MU, such as s.Pro/SUBMARINER in BLUE CONNECT, NESBp or CNR in MEDIGREEN.
VLIZ, HELCOM, CEREMA/CNR, CCMS/NIMRD, UAc/UCA (test site leads): Integrate into the national and local MPA/MSP processes.

Exploitable Result 2: D2.2 - Summary report of the existing ecological and environmental criteria

Description of result
Consolidated overview of current criteria used in marine protection and restoration, exchanged with the Deliverable 3.1 (KER 4).
Project exploitation route
Criteria included in the project database (KER 1) promoted and disseminated throughout the project. Post project: Support updates of national and regional guidelines and EU biodiversity criteria.
Target groups
Environmental agencies and authorities at different levels, MPA managers, researchers.
Sector of application
Conservation planning, ecological assessments.
Impact
Enables improved science-based and more consistent ecological decision-making across the EU seas.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Differences in interpretation; mitigated by harmonized frameworks.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
VLIZ, HELCOM, CEREMA/CNR, CCMS/NIMRD, UAc/UCA (test site leads): Further use in MSP4BIO test sites decision making. Integrate into the national and local MPA/MSP processes. CNR: Further disseminate through academic channels. UNEP MAP PAP RAC and HELCOM: Promote in Mediterranean and Baltic regional policies.

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SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 3: D2.3 - State of the art overview of the current protection and restoration measures in place

Description of result

Inventory and analysis of current marine conservation/restoration efforts in EU marine regions.

Project exploitation route

Interviews conducted across the EU sea basins with NGOs, MPA authorities, directly including stakeholder input in the report. Early open access promotion and dissemination of this report throughout the project. Use as baseline study for policy briefs and other project reports. Presentation at events. Specific fact sheet created for easier dissemination.

Post project: Feed into strategic EU wide gap analysis and building on recommendation to reach conservation and restoration targets.

Target groups

MPA and MSP authorities, MPA managers (MPA networks), NGOs.

Sector of application

Marine protection and restoration.

Impact

Provides baseline for future planning of EU Biodiversity Strategy and Ocean Pact implementation.

IPR measures

None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access, includes case study material.

Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures

-

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Exploitation activities per relevant partner
All partners: Continue dissemination of findings at events and exploitation through presentations and recommendations in upcoming MPA processes.
s.Pro/UTARTU/WWF MED/UAc/CCMS/LIZ: Use as baseline in projects such as BLUE4ALL and BLUE CONNECT.
SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 4: D3.1 - Critical review on multilevel ecological processes to improve systemic biodiversity protection and restoration strategies in Europe
Description of result
Systematic review emphasizing the need for conservation strategies that prioritize ecological functions and connectivity in marine ecosystems, aiming to improve criteria for MPAs, EBSAs, and restoration actions.
Project exploitation route
Provided baseline for ESE Framework and its component Ecological Toolkit. Presented in events and in a dedicated webinar.
Target groups
Ecologists, conservation planners, and policy/decision makers.
Sector of application
MPA/MSP, ecological research.
Impact
Enhanced effectiveness of MPAs and restoration efforts through science-based criteria.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access to ensure broad dissemination.

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Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
-
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
CNR: Lead further dissemination through scientific publications and conferences. SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 5: D3.2 - Portfolio of improved ecological criteria to be applied in systemic biodiversity protection and restoration
Description of result
Set of enhanced ecological criteria, based on KER 4, integrating connectivity, functionality, resilience.
Project exploitation route
Provided baseline for ESE Framework and its component Ecological Toolkit. Presented in events and in a dedicated webinar. Dedicated fact sheet prepared and presented. Post project: Incorporate findings into MPA design guidelines and inform EU biodiversity strategies. Embed in MPA planning tools at all levels.
Target groups
Authorities at different levels, marine ecologists, MPA and spatial planners, science/academia.
Sector of application
Conservation planning and management, MPA network design, ecological modelling.
Impact
Improves systemic effectiveness of conservation measures.
IPR measures

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None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
-
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
CNR: Lead dissemination through scientific publications and conferences. HELCOM/PAP RAC: Use in ongoing regional policies and protocols on marine conservation planning, use in projects such as PROTECT BALTIC. All partners: Integrate in ongoing MPA related processes and projects. SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 6: D3.3 - Guidance for building climate change scenarios for protection strategies
Description of result
Methodological guide to integrate climate resilience in marine protection processes.
Project exploitation route
Wide dissemination and presentation during project implementation, including at the International MPA in MSP Conference (Bodo, July 2025, see dissemination report). Discussion and with CoP members in terms of perceptions of climate change scenarios in MPAs. Dedicated fact sheet prepared and presented. Integrated in ESE Framework and its component Ecological Toolkit Post project: Include in the regional and national climate-adaptive planning frameworks.
Target groups
Environmental authorities, climate scientists, spatial planners.
Sector of application
Climate adaptation, MPAs/MSP.

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Impact
Supports climate-proofing of MSP and MPA design.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Uncertainty in projections; mitigated via scenario planning.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
CNR: Lead dissemination through scientific publications and conferences. HELCOM/PAP RAC: Embed in regional climate smart MPAs/MSP frameworks. Test site leads – further application and use in the test sites. SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 7: D3.4 - Ecological toolkit (ESE 1) for MPAs prioritization and networking
Description of result
A set of Decision Support Tools - a practical decision-support resource designed to help marine planners and policymakers identify, prioritise, and connect ecologically valuable areas for protection and restoration. It enables the application of robust, science-based ecological criteria—such as integrity, representativity, and resilience—directly into Maritime Spatial Planning and MPA network design.
Project exploitation route
Application in the test sites and validation of application results with CoPs. Demonstration session organised during ESE presentation to CoP members, A dedicated webinar organised explaining tools and providing examples of solutions. Represents the first module of ESE Framework. Specific fact sheet created for easier dissemination. Use of the outcomes of this work in Ocean Mission Blue Parks BLUE4ALL project. While some of the existing tools have been improved for the

purpose of MSP4BIO project, a specific new tool created for this Toolkit ([ABC planner](#)).

Post project: Further application in the test sites, such as Bay of Cadiz, where only initial steps of the Toolkit have been implemented. Upscale at the national/regional level for upcoming revisions of maritime spatial plans.

Target groups

MPA authorities at different levels, MSP/MPA practitioners, researchers.

Sector of application

MPA planning and its inclusion in MSP process.

Impact

Enables coherent MPA and MPA network planning taking into account cumulative pressures and impacts, and their better integration in MSP.

IPR measures

None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.

Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures

Data availability - requires ecological data input, but it offers data-ready templates and modelling tools helping with possible data gaps.

Exploitation activities per relevant partner

UTARTU/CNR: Further dissemination at events/publications. Reuse in related projects such as BLUE4ALL, BLUE CONNECT, etc. Enhance transferability of PlanWise4Blue, ABC planner, Tools4MSP across sea basins. Use in the national MPA/MSP processes (both partners already advising national authorities on protection/planning processes).

Test site leads: Use results of the applications of the Ecological Tools in MPA/MSP processes. Further application in those sites where priorities were focused on other aspects, such as governance (Bay of Cadiz).

HELCOM: Help with transferability of [HELCOM SPIA tool](#) and use results of its applications in regional MPA/MSP processes.

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SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 8: D4.1 - Criteria for the representation of the social and economic dimension of MPAs

Description of result

Socio-economic criteria for conservation planning and management. Identifies Ecosystem Services (ES) that can cover the social dimension of identification and management of MPAs, including as part of the MSP processes.

Project exploitation route

Presentation and dissemination at events, including scientific publications. Discussion with CoPs during interactions, with prioritisation exercise of ecosystem services. Validation through applications in the sites.

Post-project: Incorporate findings into MPA design guidelines and inform EU biodiversity strategies. Embed in MPA planning tools at all levels.

Target groups

Authorities, social scientists, MPA/MSP practitioners, NGOs.

Sector of application

MPA designation, social impact evaluation.

Impact

Improves MPA acceptance and just transition towards limited use of the area.

IPR measures

None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.

Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures

-

Exploitation activities per relevant partner

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All partners: Build on this work in ongoing projects such as BLUE4ALL, BLUE CONNECT and new Ocean Mission Blue parks projects.

All test sites leads: Use in the test sites and beyond to improve socio-economic aspects of MPA processes and in particular local communities and stakeholders' perspectives.

University of Cádiz (UCA): Use in further activities within Cadiz Bay test site on improving MPA management, as governance was in the focus of this test site.

SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 9: D4.2 - Guideline for the strategic and spatial measures for the nature-inclusive operation of blue economy sectors - ESE3

Description of result

Recommendations for nature-inclusive operations of blue economy sectors (tourism, fisheries, aquaculture, renewables, non-living resources) inside or in proximity of MPAs, including examples of good management practices.

Project exploitation route

Dissemination through events, publications and dedicated webinars, inviting blue economy sectoral experts. Discussion with CoP members, and validation with some of the test site industry representatives (mainly fisheries, tourism), such as in Azores, Cadiz and in the Black Sea. User-friendly, well-designed factsheets produced per sector for easier use (see Dissemination report). Integrated in ESE Framework.

Post-project: Adopt in blue economy sectors planning. Use the methodology set in the study for other blue economy sectors in follow up projects. Include in licensing and policy procedures for the blue industries.

Target groups

Industry (blue economy) stakeholders, authorities, MPA managers/ MSP planners.

Sector of application

Offshore wind, fisheries, tourism, aquaculture, non-living resources.

Impact

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Contributes to a more sustainable and nature-inclusive design of maritime industry activities inside or in proximity of MPAs, contribution to more sustainable ocean multi-use.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Sectors buy-in — industry involved to some extent during project implementation.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
<p>Test site leads: Further engage with blue economy sectors in the test sites to apply the good practices outlined in the report. Further upscale at sea basin level according to Deliverable 5.4 (KER 14).</p> <p>HELCOM/PAP RAC: Further promote and adopt these guidelines at the sea basin level.</p> <p>s.Pro: bring in project results in the ongoing and upcoming multi-use projects such as ULTFARMS, and other SUBMARINER initiatives. Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.</p>

Exploitable Result 10: D4.3 - Trade-offs method for protection and restoration in MSP – ESE3
Description of result
Decision-support method for evaluating trade-offs providing a portfolio of mapping tools, to facilitate this process by allowing participants to contribute data and insights in an accessible, user-friendly platform. Key role in the process of integrating MPAs in MSP processes.
Project exploitation route
Trade-off exercise performed with CoPs (test site specific stakeholders). Concrete results obtained in almost all test sites, validated with stakeholders. Feedback received from CoPs who evaluated this method as one of the most useful ones in the MPA/MSP processes. Presented in webinars and meetings at local, national, regional and EU levels (Dissemination report). Focusing mainly on training and

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<p>application of SeaSketch (test site leads trained during II project General Assembly), an interactive online mapping tool, to facilitate participatory process in an accessible, user-friendly manner. A company in Spain started using SeaSketch, influenced by the work of the Cadiz test site.</p> <p>Post project: Integrate as adopted approach in MPA/MSP processes in the test sites and beyond. Use results of the SeaSketch (open access) exercise in the national MPS/MSP processes.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>
<p>MSP/MPA authorities, MPA/MSP planners.</p>
<p>Sector of application</p>
<p>MPA/MSP, blue economy.</p>
<p>Impact</p>
<p>By involving stakeholders directly, supports transparent, informed MPA/MSP decision making. Ensures that diverse perspectives and traditional knowledge are integrated into the marine spatial planning process. Supports balanced, informed choices that optimize environmental, economic, and social outcomes, fostering collaborative solutions that align marine conservation goals with sustainable development.</p>
<p>IPR measures</p>
<p>None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.</p>
<p>Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures</p>
<p>Getting familiar with the tool — recorded webinar publicly available and examples from test sites included in ESE Framework.</p>
<p>Exploitation activities per relevant partner</p>
<p>All partners: promote this methodology and test site results and SeaSketch training webinar for further use and uptake.</p> <p>Test site leads: Further disseminate and promote the approach and test site results with authorities for future use in MPA/MSP processes.</p> <p>SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.</p>

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Exploitable Result 11: D4.4 - Strategic Guidance on the integration of MPA and MSP on multiple governance and ecosystem levels
Description of result
Comprehensive guidance for integrating Marine Protected Areas (MPAs) into Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) across various governance levels and ecosystems.
Project exploitation route
Preparation of this deliverable involved mobilisation of almost all project partners, conducting analysis of the EU Maritime Spatial Plans and screening them evaluating level of integration with marine conservation. Final assessment was produced in cooperation with MPA/MSP authorities from each country selected for screening, through direct input and interviews. The report was disseminated among authorities once prepared. An additional, well designed, easy to read product is available – Guide for MPA/MSP integration, already disseminated and available on MSP4BIO website . Disseminated and presented at different events/publications, including at the International MPA in MSP conference (Bodo, July 2025). Integrated in ESE Framework. Post project: Further dissemination of the guide at regional and national level, directly with authorities and MPA/MSP actors.
Target groups
MPA/MSP authorities, environmental agencies, and marine conservation organizations.
Sector of application
MPA/MSP, maritime governance.
Impact
Enhanced coherence between MPA and MSP processes, considering conservation more than a layer in MSP, leading to more effective biodiversity conservation and sustainable maritime planning.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.

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Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Barrier: Diverse governance structures across regions. Mitigation: Tailor guidance to specific regional contexts and provide case studies demonstrating successful integration.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
All partners: Distribute the designed version of the MPA/MSP integration Guide to the authorities, especially those that were contacted for feedback and co-creation of the level of MPA/MSP integration for specific countries. SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 12: D4.5 - Integrated Ecological-Socio-Economic Management Framework - ESE Step-by- Step guidance (with test site examples and lessons learned)
Description of result
The key component/outcome of the MSP4BIO project, which provides a structured step-by-step approach to integrate ecological considerations into decision-making processes, ensuring sustainable use of marine and coastal resources. The framework is composed of three modules comprising different tools that guide users through data collection, analysis, scenario development, and impact assessment. These tools—such as Tools4MSP, PlanWise4Blue, Participatory mapping – trade-off scenario development etc, in addition to the EU-wide data base, MPA/MSP integration guide and policy coherence solutions—enable planners and stakeholders to evaluate trade-offs, assess cumulative impacts, and optimize spatial plans in line with conservation goals. These actionable tools were co-developed and validated with test-site specific stakeholders (CoPs), in each of the MSP4BIO test sites, integrating site specific solutions as examples of ESE applications.
Project exploitation route
The ESE Framework has been fully based on co-creation processes in the test sites through direct engagement with CoPs (site specific stakeholders). From identification of the test site needs (management questions) to the co-development of tools and their application in the test sites, stakeholder input and validation has been a key component of the process. ESE Framework was presented to the CoPs

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at different stages, from initial draft to the final version, and feedback was collected through dedicated surveys. Showcasing ESE Framework was part of the application of tools in the test sites and validation of obtained solutions. ESE Framework, as the final result of MSP4BIO, is still to be widely presented and disseminated. To facilitate that process, a user-friendly online website platform was created (in addition to the document promised in the Grant Agreement), embedded in MSP4BIO website. A dedicated well-designed brief was prepared for easier dissemination. The final ESE Framework was presented during the MSP4BIO Final event, as well as in specific test site validation events, at the International MPA in MSP conference, to the MED MSP CoP etc. Further presentations/publications are planned post project (see Dissemination report).

Post project: The framework is highly transferable and can be adapted to other policy domains or governance contexts beyond MPA in MSP, particularly in areas where co-creation, systems thinking, and integrated planning approaches are required. The current structure also allows for new questions, modules, and stakeholder inputs to be incorporated over time, supporting its evolution in response to emerging needs and challenges.

Target groups

MSP practitioners, MPA managers, MPA/MSP authorities, industries, research and academia, NGOs.

Sector of application

MPA/MSP

Impact

Advancing the knowledge base and decision-support capacity within ecosystem-sensitive planning processes. With its participatory origin, flexible design, and technical scalability, the framework is well-positioned to support future efforts toward more integrated, adaptive, and inclusive marine governance.

IPR measures

None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.

Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures

Institutional silos, complexity of ESE Framework — addressed via integration guidelines including stakeholder engagement and institutional cooperation aspects,

as well as clear examples from case studies. Clear step by step guideline available for the use of ESE Framework.

Exploitation activities per relevant partner

CNR: Disseminate through scientific networks and channels and apply in the national MSP processes. Maintain ESE website platform.

All partners: Disseminate across test sites/national level/regions for uptake in MSP processes.

SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 13: D5.3 - Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration

Description of result

Results of application of the ESE Framework to co-develop and validate site-specific solutions for biodiversity protection and restoration within MSP, involving local stakeholders.

Project exploitation route

Site specific solutions have been developed based on the needs defined with the stakeholders in the test sites, and through co-creation and validation process of project tools and methodologies, as well as solutions resulting from applications of ESE Framework and its tools. Solutions were presented as ESE demonstrators in a dedicated webinar, and validated through local validation events (conducted in three sites) and during the project Final event including a validation workshop.

Post project: Uptake of project solutions for official MPA/MSP processes, such as in Azores (expansion of MPA resulting from project applications sent to the Government for approval), Cadiz (governance solutions, in particular for institutional coordination mechanism considered to continue after project end), Baltic Sea (specific Baltic solutions discussed with the HELCOM WGs and taken on board for regional processes and projects such as NESBp, PROTECT Baltic) etc. Solutions brought forward and continued processes in all test sites and upscaled at sea basin level in line with recommendations available in KER 14.

Target groups

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Local and national MSP authorities, conservation authorities and practitioners, and community stakeholders.
Sector of application
MSP/MPA, and community-based conservation.
Impact
Showcasing applicability and scalability of ESE Framework and its tools through their implementation in different ecological, socio-economic and governance contexts. Providing concrete examples of planning solutions from the real-world sites, co-created and validated by site specific stakeholders and their possible adoption in the official MPA/MSP processes.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access to encourage replication.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Limited local capacity for implementation - Stakeholder involved from the early project stages, with demonstration sessions supporting local stakeholders and authorities.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
All test sites: Bring forward site specific solutions to national/regional authorities. Same as in above explained post project exploitation route. SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

Exploitable Result 14: D5.4 - Final recommendations, transferability and scale-up of effective biodiversity mainstreaming in MSP
Description of result
A concise easy to read report providing results of the cross-test site analysis and advise on the transferability of results and potentials and barriers for its upscaling. Recommendations are presented for each of the European Sea Basins highlighting key challenges, opportunities, and enabling conditions necessary for success, to provide the basis for scaling up across Europe.

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Project exploitation route
This report is based on the test site results, co-developed and validated with site specific stakeholders.
Target groups
National and regional environmental and MSP authorities, MPA/MSP practitioners, NGOs, blue economy sectors
Sector of application
MPA and MSP policy implementation at the regional seas level
Impact
The expected impact of this deliverable is to enable the broader uptake and long-term application of MSP4BIO's biodiversity mainstreaming approaches by providing actionable recommendations, tested tools, and pathways for replication. By supporting transferability and scale-up across diverse marine regions and governance contexts, it contributes to strengthening ecosystem-based MSP practices and aligning them with EU biodiversity and climate goals.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Time mismatch with MSP preparation cycles, limited uptake by decision makers. Mitigated by inclusion of CoPs in the development and validation of solutions in line with the initially developed management questions, as well as the final presentation and demonstration of tools and their usability in the MPA/MSP processes.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
All test site leads/HELCOM/PAP RAC/CCMS: active contribution to MPA/MSP processes at the regional level through implementation of recommendations. SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.

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Exploitable Result 15: D6.1 - State of the art on key barriers and levers for policy coherence
Description of result
A report identifying barriers and levers of coherent implementation of an overarching policy objective (biodiversity protection) within the existing environmental and sectoral policies, in particular those that may have contradicting objectives. It highlighted the potential and limitations of the integrative policy frameworks.
Project exploitation route
Interviews conducted with different policy actors during report preparation, at the national, regional seas and EU levels. Served as basis for policy coherence solutions (KER16). Presented to DG MARE, regional conventions, and national governments.
Target groups
EU institutions, regional sea organizations, national authorities.
Sector of application
Policy (biodiversity and related sectoral policies)
Impact
Provides crucial insights on policy solutions needed to address identified gaps, in line with identified barriers and levers.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Policy inertia — addressed with compelling evidence and timing with policy cycles, in particular with the adoption of the EU Ocean Pact.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms. WWF EPO: Advocate for inclusion in EU policy reviews.

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HELCOM/PAP RAC: Implement in the revisions of regional policies.

Exploitable Result 16: D6.2 - Future directions for the EU, regional seas and national implementation of the EU Biodiversity Strategy in the coastal and marine regions
Description of result
Concrete policy solutions aimed at strengthening biodiversity integration into EU marine and maritime policies, addressing institutional, technical, and financial challenges.
Project exploitation route
Engage with EU policymakers through the MSP4BIO Final event and validation workshop, the joint policy event with the CrossGov project, disseminating across regional sea convention groups involved in project implementation (HELCOM VASAB MSP, PAP RAC MSP WG) as well as directly among MSP4BIO CoPs. Contribute to future policy revisions and using diversity of partnership for diverse exploitation aspects. Post project: Promote further during Ocean Pact implementation, including Ocean Act. Bring up with authorities participating in the prioritisation and final shaping of policy solutions for their adoption and implementation.
Target groups
EU institutions, national governments, NGOs, and policy advocacy NGOs.
Sector of application
Marine policy development, environmental regulation, and biodiversity conservation.
Impact

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Improved policy coherence MPA/MSP and across sectors and increased effectiveness in marine biodiversity conservation efforts.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access to facilitate policy uptake.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
Resistance to policy change due to conflicting interests - Discussion of solutions in different fora, at different levels, during project implementation (regional level, authorities, CoPs). Provided evidence-based arguments demonstrating long-term benefits of solutions.
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
SPRO: Submission to the selected exploitation platforms (EU MSP Platform, MPA CN, Ocean Mission, Zenodo). HELCOM/PAP RAC/ CCMS/WWF: Advocate for policy solution adoption and implementation at EU and national levels.

Exploitable Result 17: D6.3 - Policy solutions for MSP based on the science-policy dialogues
Description of result
Synthesis of the main policy-oriented outcomes from the Science-Policy dialogues held between May 2023 and May 2025. Results outline actionable recommendations for policy coherence based on stakeholder’s feedback, and a mapping of EU-funded projects and initiatives main resources for a better integration of biodiversity into MSP.
Project exploitation route
Four Think tank meetings engaging with relevant project representatives, policy makers and experts, have been organised mapping project tools and their contribution to policy implementation, as well as co-creating clustering results and recommendations. Main results presented during MED MSP CoP meeting, HELCOM WGs, at BLUE CONNECT partner meetings and BioAgora meeting.

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<p>MSP4BIO final conference in Venice (2-4 July 2025) during a specific session dedicated to cross-project collaboration and Think Tank results.</p> <p>Post project: Further work among projects leading to specific cross-project recommendations will be done through BioAgora initiative, already building its work on the outcomes of the Think tanks. EU DGs taking on board cross-project analysis on tool mapping and their contribution to policy implementation.</p>	
Target groups	
EU decision and policy makers, national/regional (sea basin)/local Governments.	
Sector of application	
Support to policy implementation	
Impact	
Improve identification of synergies among EU-funded projects and explore future collaborations post-project. Improved policy coherence MPA/MSP and across sectors and increased effectiveness in marine biodiversity conservation efforts.	
IPR measures	
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.	
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures	
-	
Exploitation activities per relevant partner	
<p>WWF MED/SPRO: Continue alignment with BioAgora clustering initiative for uptake of Think tank outcomes. Continue its work in BLUE CONNECT project.</p> <p>All partners: Disseminate results of this cross-project work in relevant ongoing and future projects.</p> <p>SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.</p>	

Exploitable Result 18: D6.4 - Joint policy recommendations	
Description of result	

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<p>A well designed, easy-to-read brief - result of collaboration with 7 other projects and initiatives related to MPA and MSP (MSP4BIO, MPA Europe, CrossGov, MSP Green, REGINA-MSP, MSP-OR, and eMSP NBSR), primarily in the MSP4BIO Science-Policy Dialogue Think tanks.</p>
<p>Project exploitation route</p>
<p>These recommendations are based on different exchanges among 7 projects, engaging primarily through Think tank meetings, but also through other events, concluding with a cross-project session at the MSP4BIO Final event. These recommendations have been presented to EU policy makers, at HELCOM WGs, at BLUE CONNECT partner meetings and in communication with BioAgora.</p> <p>Post project: Further work among projects leading to specific cross-project recommendations will be done through BioAgora initiative, already building its work on the outcomes of the Think tanks. An easy to read designed brief was created for this deliverable, and its dissemination and presentation will be prioritised by project partners and key multipliers.</p>
<p>Target groups</p>
<p>EU decision and policy makers, national/regional (sea basin)/local authorities.</p>
<p>Sector of application</p>
<p>Policy (preparation, revision and better alignment)</p>
<p>Impact</p>
<p>Joint recommendation will contribute to a stronger evidence base for decision-making, powered by support from 7 different EU funded projects, resulting from cooperation and project clustering exercises. With a specific section on the call for policy makers, providing specific recommendations for the ongoing/upcoming MSFD and MSP directives, it is exploiting current momentum for effective revision of these policies and their better alignment. It is expected that specific recommendations will be taken on board for the implementation of the EU Ocean Pact. The document will also serve as a strategic reference for future clustering initiatives, such as BioAgora.</p>
<p>IPR measures</p>
<p>None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.</p>
<p>Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures</p>

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Exploitation activities per relevant partner
<p>WWF MED and WWF EPO/SPRO: a dedicated press-release will be issues in September/October, informing about these joint recommendations, and widely disseminated through the social media by MSP4BIO project and communication partners. Advocate for inclusion in EU policy reviews.</p> <p>SPRO: Submission of the report to the exploitation platforms.</p>

Exploitable Result 19: D7.5 - Policy Brief
Description of result
<p>A concise deliverable presenting an overview of identified challenges for biodiversity mainstreaming in MSP, solutions that the project offers to address these challenges highlighting key policy recommendation. An additional easy-to-read and well-designed brief summarising the key policy recommendations from the project has been created.</p>
Project exploitation route
<p>The work towards policy recommendations has already been discussed and promoted through MSP4BIO Final event, joint policy session with CrossGov and other projects, as well as future high-profile policy events such as the EU Maritime Day, EU Ocean Days, Blue Parks workshops, and others deemed relevant. Additionally, MSP4BIO Science-Policy dialogues Think tanks have been established at the beginning of the project to coordinate with other EU-funded projects to align messaging and jointly advocate for policy changes. Think tank meetings, as well as regional platforms such as HELCOM WGs, MED MSP CoP, Black Sea regional meeting involving Black Sea Commission facilitated direct engagement with national ministries, regional sea conventions, and EU institutions to ensure policy uptake.</p> <p>Post project: The project will widely disseminate the policy brief through strategic channels, ensuring it reaches key decision-makers and stakeholders. The brief will be published on project and partner websites, shared via EU knowledge platforms (e.g., EU MSP Platform, Mission Ocean platform), as well as Zenodo and MPA CN. Final Policy recommendations will be presented in the next EU MSP WG.</p>
Target groups

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Policy actors at different levels (national, regional, EU), MPA/MSP/MSFD authorities.
Sector of application
Policy (MSP, marine conservation)
Impact
The policy brief will contribute to a stronger evidence base for decision-making, ensuring that maritime spatial planning, conservation and sectoral policies are aligned with scientific findings and test site best practices. It is expected that specific recommendations will be taken on board for the implementation of the EU Ocean Pact. The document will also serve as a strategic reference for future funding and legislative initiatives, at both national and EU levels. Given extensive discussions that took place with HELCOM WGs on MSP and Biodiversity, a dedicated Baltic policy brief was produced.
IPR measures
None foreseen. Relevant publications are open access.
Possible barriers to exploitation activities and mitigation measures
-
Exploitation activities per relevant partner
<p>HELCOM: Bringing forward final policy recommendations already discussed and evaluated by Baltic Sea authorities. Implement regional recommendations as part of ongoing regional actions. Build on the recommendations in the ongoing NESBp project.</p> <p>PAP RAC: Bringing forward relevant policy solutions already presented to the MED MSP CoP. Follow up on this work in the UNEP MAP PAP RAC MSP Working Group.</p> <p>SPRO: Provide all the materials to the exploitation platforms and initiatives (Zenodo, MSP Platform, MPA CN, Ocean Mission Platform, BioAgora etc). Maintain MSP4BIO website and present recommendation in all relevant for a in connection with related projects and initiatives.</p>

WWF MED and WWF EPO: Actively promote the final recommendations including in the relevant EU and Mediterranean bodies that they are part of, such as EU MSP WG, UNEP MAP etc. Advocate for inclusion in EU policy reviews.

All partners: Actively promote the final recommendations for implementation in their networks and supporting decision making at different levels.

4.7 Project Legacy in MSP4BIO test sites

Test Site Legacy and Insights

MSP4BIO worked across six test sites representing diverse ecological, governance, and socio-economic contexts. Application of ESE tools in the sites produced results validated with site-specific stakeholders (Communities of Practice) which are expected to be further exploited in the sites and national processes resulting in improved policies and governance, new/expanded MPAs and their effective management, cooperation with stakeholders and participatory processes as well as integrating better socio-economic aspects and climate change scenarios in MPA processes.

4.6.1 Baltic Sea (sea-basin wide test site):

Key Opportunities:

- Strong regional cooperation through HELCOM.
- Active MSP processes with focus on ecosystem-based management.
- Ongoing activities on the identification of pressures and cumulative impact assessments, and their better integration in MSP/MPAs processes.
- Ongoing activities and projects on achieving biodiversity goals both in terms of spatial coverage and their effectiveness (e.g. Protect Baltic, ongoing).

Exploitation Potential:

- **Enhance Cross-Border MSP:** Use MSP4BIO tools to facilitate transboundary planning efforts, ensuring coherent biodiversity objectives across borders.
- **Implement Climate Scenarios:** Apply the guidance for building climate change scenarios to assess future impacts on marine biodiversity.
- **Adopt Trade-Offs Methodology:** Utilize the trade-offs method for protection and restoration to balance ecological and socio-economic interests.

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- **Use Cumulative Impacts Assessments/Impact levels in MPAs:** Inform the MSP processes and incorporate results into green infrastructure maps, as highlighted in the objectives of the Baltic Sea Regional MSP Road Map.
- **Include MSP4BIO cumulative impact assessment tools in the future trainings:** expand capacity-building initiatives at the regional level to train stakeholders and MSP practitioners on using tools like SPIA in marine protected areas and applying its results.
- **Transfer results of ESE applications:** proposed solution in the Baltic Sea by using the trade-off analysis leverages the ESE framework to address specific human activities, such as bottom trawling, while integrating trade-offs with ecosystem service valuations. This approach provides a structured methodology that can be adapted for other sea basins.
- **More detailed recommendations available in [Deliverable 5.3 Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration](#)**

Strategic Value of the site for exploitation at sea-basin level and beyond:

- Located in a **highly cooperative regional sea** (HELCOM) with strong environmental governance.
- Enables applications of **cross-border biodiversity integration** in MSP.
- Supports ecosystem-based management under **existing Baltic-wide biodiversity commitments**.

4.6.2 Northern-West Mediterranean (trans-national Italy-France test site)

Key Opportunities

- Shared commitment to marine conservation under the **Pelagos Sanctuary** and **Barcelona Convention**.
- Existing collaborative efforts in **cross-border MSP and MPAs**.
- High biodiversity value and increasing pressure from maritime uses (shipping, tourism, energy, etc.), presenting an opportunity for targeted conservation and sustainable planning/protection.

Exploitation Potential:

- **Support Regional Policy Integration:** Further enhance cross-border research and policy cooperation. Continue application of the MSP4BIO integrated ecological-socio-economic (ESE) framework to harmonize biodiversity planning across national borders.

- **Climate-Responsive Planning:** Further assess and describe Climate change incidence for both NWMed priority targets (i.e. Marine Mammals and VMEs) integrating science-grounded projections (e.g. biotic velocities) in line with recent development of knowledge about these species. Results achieved in the site ensure a quick and protocolled CC inclusion in the in-development MSP plan in the NWMed, making the sub-region one of the few sites turned toward a more climate-smart future.
- **Build partnerships to further apply MSP4BIO results:** work with regional and international regulatory organizations such as IHO or GFCM which are relevant to address pressures on cetaceans or on VMEs.
- **Continue deep-sea activities:** MSP4BIO results in the site will feed the lack of exploration and knowledge that will be particularly useful to better assess the connectivity and the deep-sea species dynamics.
- **Continue activities on establishing the network of the strictly protected MPAs:** The participatory mapping tool developed through the project will allow stakeholders and scientists to suggest other areas to be protected and to support States' administration in the development of the strict protection network.
- **More detailed recommendations available in [Deliverable 5.3 Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration](#)**

Strategic Value of the site for exploitation at sea-basin level and beyond:

This test site offers a real-world laboratory for applying MSP4BIO tools to international collaboration, where differing legal and governance systems must converge on common marine conservation goals. Exploiting results here supports further trans-national cooperation and climate smart marine planning and management, as well as broader Mediterranean integration under EU and regional sea conventions.

4.6.3 Black Sea (transboundary test site Bulgaria-Romania)

Key Opportunities:

- Identified needs in both countries to further enhance activities on cumulative impact assessments and its integration in marine spatial planning and MPAs management.
- Need for enhanced cross-border cooperation in MSP and coherent MPAs.

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- Rich biodiversity with significant conservation challenges.

Exploitation Potential:

- **Strengthen Transboundary Collaboration:** Utilize MSP4BIO findings on MPA and MSP integration to foster cooperation and strengthen a common integrated regional approach to MSP process, in particular between Bulgaria and Romania. Expand cooperation and project involvement to remaining non-EU countries. Align proposed MSP and MPA management integration with existing regional strategies, such as the Black Sea Convention and the Common Maritime Agenda.
- **Adopt and further apply the trade-off approach:** to enhance and facilitate the wider stakeholder involvement in the MPA/MSP decision-making at national level and develop consensus-based approaches to MPAs management and coherence at cross-border and transboundary regional level.
- **Contribute to capacity building activities:** use MSP4BIO dissemination and knowledge transfer materials to empower local and regional stakeholders with the knowledge and tools necessary for effective participation in MSP and MPA processes, engaging in continuous dialogue with regional key actors.
- **More detailed recommendations available in [Deliverable 5.3 Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration](#).**

Strategic Value of the site for exploitation at sea-basin level and beyond:

- Represents an area with underdeveloped MSP and important biodiversity and fisheries challenges .
- Offers an opportunity to apply MSP4BIO tools in emerging policy and spatial planning/MPAs management settings with transboundary needs.
- Supports EU integration, regional cooperation, and alignment with Black Sea Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and the Common Maritime Agenda
- **Can serve as replication model for the Bulgarian and Romanian Demonstration Sites in the BLUE CONNECT project.**

4.6.4 North Sea (Belgium)

Key Opportunities:

- High data availability and strong institutional capacity.
- Existing MSP frameworks that can integrate MSP4BIO tools.
- Ongoing work on pelagic habitats and

Exploitation Potential:

- **Integrate the ESE Framework in the future national MSP process:** Embed the Ecological-Socio-Economic (ESE) framework into the future MSP revision cycles to enhance biodiversity considerations, in with concrete recommendations highlighted in Deliverable 5.3¹³.
- **Enhance Regional Sea cooperation:** Existing regional platforms such as OSPAR are useful framework to investigate climate change at regional scales (data and methods) and to provide a consistent approach across Contracting Parties. Especially for mobile species, large scale analyses and transboundary cooperation will be needed to investigate the effects of climate change.
- **Capacity building:** Further disseminate MSP4BIO capacity building materials for training end-users and their better uptake.
- **More details and recommendations available in [Deliverable 5.3 Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration](#).**
- **Upscale at sub-basin level:** See more in Deliverable 5.4 (under review).

Strategic Value of the site for exploitation at sea-basin level and beyond:

- Advances MSP process in the EU, offering a mature legislative and data-rich environment.
- Ideal for testing ecological tools into well-established MSP processes.
- Can serve as a replication model for other North Sea countries and heavily used sea basins.

4.6.5 North-East Atlantic (Azores – Graciosa Island)

Key Opportunities:

- Unique biodiversity and extensive marine areas.
- Ongoing strong commitment to MPA designation/expansion and creation of highly/fully protected MPAs.
- Emerging MSP processes with potential for integrating conservation priorities.

Exploitation potential:

¹³ Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration

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- **Extension of the MPA in the test site:** Adoption of the proposed extension of the MPA in the test site (see Deliverable 5.3 for more details) by the authorities in the ongoing MPA review process (proposal sent to the authorities).
- **Build on and enhance further the stakeholder engagement processes established in MSP4BIO:** Engage stakeholders from various sectors, including MSP planners, MPA managers, environmental NGOs, and representatives from key industries such as fisheries and energy, to foster collaboration and ensure effective implementation of methodologies for marine protection, such as in BLUE CONNECT project.
- **Address Policy Coherence:** Adopt and implement identified policy solutions for MPA/MSP policy incoherence and further integration.
- **More details and recommendations available in [Deliverable 5.3 Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration](#).**

Strategic Value of the site for exploitation at sea-basin level and beyond:

- Advanced activities on stakeholder engagement in the marine conservation and planning processes, including local communities and citizens.
- Many ongoing and new projects approved in this area, continuing the work of MSP4BIO project.
- Can serve as a replication model for other parts of Macaronesia such as in the ongoing Ocean Mission BLUE CONNECT project.

4.6.6 North-East Atlantic (Spain – Cadiz Bay)

Key opportunities:

- Identified needs for clear governance system and policy solutions for the area validated by stakeholders.
- Continued cooperation with the local community, including fishermen.
- Stakeholders commitment to preserving traditional and cultural value of the area.

Exploitation potential:

- **Further apply the ESE 1:** Follow-up on preparatory work and utilize the ESE ecological toolkit to define conservation objectives and measures for effective

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management of the area, ensuring both environmental sustainability and human well-being.

- **Build on and enhance further the stakeholder engagement processes established in MSP4BIO:** Engage stakeholders from various sectors, including MSP planners, MPA managers, environmental NGOs, and representatives from key industries such as fisheries and energy, to foster collaboration and ensure effective implementation of methodologies.
- **Address Policy Coherence:** Support Adoption and implementation of identified policy solutions for MPA/MSP policy incoherence.
- **Implement Nature-Based Solutions in blue economy:** Further demonstrate how safeguarding traditional economic activities and applying nature-based solutions in the natural park contributes to biodiversity.
- **More details and recommendations available in [Deliverable 5.3 Site specific solutions for accelerating biodiversity protection and restoration](#).**

Strategic Value of the site for exploitation at sea-basin level and beyond:

- **Ecological Significance:** The Bay of Cádiz is a diverse, integrated coastal and marine ecosystem.
- **Socio-Economic Dynamics:** The region faces challenges due to its dense population and socio-economic pressures, including traditional shell-fishing activities and tourism.
- **Policy Integration:** The site offers an opportunity to address conflicts within the nominal MPA of the Bay of Cádiz, which, despite strategic objectives, lacks effective implementation and serve as a model for areas facing similar challenges.

The test sites can serve as transferable models for upscale at the sea basin level or other sea basins. Their legacy includes documented processes, feedback loops, clear site-specific solutions and stakeholder engagement frameworks.

5. Long-term sustainability of project results

Linking Exploitation to Upscaling and Transferability

The MSP4BIO Exploitation Roadmap is designed not only to guide the continued use of the project's outputs but also to serve as a foundation for scaling up their application and transferring them to the sea-basin level but also to other regions and policy contexts. Building on insights from the six test sites and the co-developed tools and methods, as well as on the outcomes of the Deliverable 5.4 (Final recommendations, transferability and scale-up of effective biodiversity mainstreaming in MSP) the following upscaling and transferability recommendations are proposed:

- **Mainstreaming the ESE Framework in MSP practice:** Encourage EU Member States and regional authorities to integrate the ESE Management Framework and joint policy recommendations into national MSP cycles, with tailored adjustments reflecting local ecological, socio-economic, and governance conditions.
- **Replication in other Sea Basins:** Lessons learned from MSP4BIO test sites can inform biodiversity integration in MSP at sea basin level (all five sea basins represented in the project) but also in underrepresented regions such as the Eastern Mediterranean, and Macaronesia. Partnerships with existing regional sea conventions can support alignment with basin-wide strategies.
- **Policy alignment and EU-Level adoption:** Advocate for the incorporation of MSP4BIO's policy recommendations into the ongoing review of the MSFD Directive, the upcoming review of the MSP directive, national MSP reviews/update processes, the Nature Restoration Law implementation roadmap, and the post-2030 EU Biodiversity Strategy.
- **Transfer to cross-sectoral Blue Economy planning:** Promote the use of the project's tools in other domains such as offshore renewable energy siting, sustainable aquaculture planning, sustainable fisheries, reinforcing biodiversity safeguards in multi-use contexts.
- **Training and peer-learning:** Facilitate structured knowledge transfer through dissemination of recorded webinars, capacity-building workshops, university modules, and twinning activities with authorities and planners in non-participating countries.
- **Digital integration and interoperability:** MSP4BIO ensured that the tools are compatible with key digital infrastructures (e.g. MSP Data Framework, EMODnet, Digital Twin of the Ocean) maximising usability and integration with existing data systems.

To ensure continuity beyond the project's lifecycle:

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- **ESE Framework website/tools maintenance:** CNR will keep alive and maintain the ESE Framework website (<https://ese.tools4msp.eu/>). CNR/UTARTU will keep specific Decision-supporting tools, improved/updated in the course of MSP4BIO project constituting Ecological Toolkit ESE1 (such as Tools4MSP, ABC planner, PlanWise4Blue etc) updated and maintained, available and open access. SUBMARINER Network/s.Pro, in collaboration with core project partners, will assume responsibility for hosting and updating the MPA CN website.
- **Planned post-project communication legacy:** Plan are already in place for the continuity of key dissemination assets (e.g. keeping the website online, archiving key outputs on open repositories) and encourage partners to continue promoting results beyond the project’s end.

Monitoring Exploitation Impact (KPIs)

Table 15 Monitoring exploitation success

Indicator	Target (within 5 years post-project)
MSP processes using MSP4BIO tools	≥5
References in policy documents	≥3
Training or awareness events	≥5
Tools downloads/users	≥1000
Collaborative proposals developed	≥1

Together, these steps will maximise the systemic impact of MSP4BIO by embedding biodiversity-led MSP into long-term marine governance and planning strategies at European and national levels.

4.8 Risk assessment and mitigation strategies

Early in the MSP4BIO project implementation, main risks and mitigation strategy have been prepared and discussed throughout the project, organising work in a way to take potential risks into account and minimise them.

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Table 16 Mitigation actions implemented to address potential impact risks.

Risk	Mitigation Strategy (already implemented)
Limited policy uptake	Early engagement with EU, regional seas and national authorities and related projects. Coordination of science-policy dialogue Think tanks and of joint policy recommendations with sister projects. Specific policy briefs produced.
Low stakeholder usage of ESE Framework/ESE tools	Engagement with CoPs thought project implementation, including user testing, feedback integration, and provision of recorded webinars/trainings and demonstrations.
Data gaps or low interoperability	Promotion of standardised protocols; data base established and promoted early in the project. Open access of all project outcomes. Coordination with EMODnet and Copernicus Marine Service.
Loss of momentum post-project	Exploitation actions taken early on, engaging with end users, policy actors at different levels, and presenting results at different events. Erly engagement with exploitation platforms and clustering initiatives (e.g. BioAgora). Participation in the Ocean Pact consultations and discussion of final results in light of the Ocean Pact implementation. EU/SUBMARINER exploitation for continuous engagement and visibility.

4.9 Partnership and Collaboration

Sustained exploitation will rely on:

- **Support by strategic partnerships:** By EU agencies, regional seas organisations (HELCOM, UNEP/MAP - Barcelona Convention, Black Sea Commission – project partners), and international bodies.
- **Project clusters:** Contribution to BioAgora clustering work and continued collaboration with Horizon Europe and LIFE projects focused on nature restoration, marine planning, and climate adaptation.
- **Cross-sector alliances:** Engaging fisheries, renewable energy, and tourism sectors in MSP co-creation processes to apply results in real contexts.
- **Capacity building networks/MOOCs:** MOOCs MPA/MSP module integrating MSP4BIO results, available online. Work with universities and training academies to embed MSP4BIO outputs into curricula and lifelong learning initiatives.

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4.10 Conclusion

The MSP4BIO Exploitation Roadmap sets a clear direction for the sustainable uptake of its results, reinforcing the project's core mission of improving biodiversity outcomes through science-informed, stakeholder-driven MSP. By engaging targeted actors, providing practical tools, planning solutions, and fostering policy alignment, MSP4BIO will continue to influence marine conservation well beyond its official completion.

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5. Annexes

Annex A: Feedback infographic on CoP interactions 2024

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Annex B: Feedback infographic on CoP interactions 2025

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COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

GENERAL SATISFACTION

Overall experience 1 **4.8/5**

Addressing needs and priorities of test sites 2 **4.8/5**

Project implementation and relevance 3

- Bridging marine conservation and MSP **4/5**
- Usefulness of MSP4BIO in professional work for CoPs **4.1/5**
- The project's synthesis of data and methods is a valuable resource for both science and management. In the Azores, MSP4BIO CoP agreed on an MPA expansion, a great success.
- Knowledge Sharing **4/5**
- Contribution to regional and national MSP processes **4.5/5**

It strengthened cross-border cooperation by compiling and sharing existing knowledge, while also revealing key information gaps that must be addressed for effective MSP implementation. In the Baltic Sea, MSP4BIO tools have already been validated in HELCOM working groups.

USEFULNESS OF KEY RESULTS

Implementation of MSP4BIO tools 4

All MSP4BIO tools have been implemented in CoPs with the *Portfolio of ecological criteria, policy coherence solutions, test site solutions, the Ecological Toolkit and Nature inclusive design of blue economy sectors* being used the most across test sites. Trade-off approaches and SeaSketch were very much appreciated across all test sites and CoPs show interest to use these tools in the future.

Usefulness of tools in respective CoP context 5

Ranking of tools:

- 4.5/5 ESE Framework
- 4.5/5 Nature inclusive design of BE sectors
- 4.5/5 Policy Coherence Solutions
- 4.5/5 Test Site Solutions
- 4/5 Ecological Toolkit (ESE)
- 4/5 Climate-Smart MPAs Guidance
- 3.6/5 Portfolio of improved Ecological Criteria
- 3.5/5 Socio-economic Criteria for MPAs (ESE2)

Sharing of MSP4BIO tools beyond CoPs 6

Two CoPs shared MSP4BIO tools with relevant partners from their network. One CoP is still planning on sharing MSP4BIO tools, two reported they did not share tools.

COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

COMMUNITIES OF PRACTICE FEEDBACK 2025

- Positive feedback
- Feedback to learn from
- Suggestions

CONTRIBUTION TO POLICY OR PRACTICE

Influence of MSP4BIO on policy processes 7

CoPs shared that MSP4BIO already has or will influence the following processes in the future:

- National or regional MSP plans
- Marine protection or restoration strategies
- Cross-border cooperation initiatives
- Institutional capacity-building
- Policy development and governance

One CoP reported that none of the above have been influenced until now.

Potential for Uptake of the MSP4BIO tools 8

- The Azores test site has already taken up site-specific solutions by agreeing on an MPA expansion for the area.
- In the Baltic Sea, authorities are already building on MSP4BIO ESE1 and policy solutions.
- CoPs expressed interest to implement trade-off approaches and SeaSketch in the future.

- A transboundary synthesis on marine mammals and VME-related issues could support the launch of a CoP in the Pelagos Sanctuary.
- Foster public-public, public-private, and public-community partnerships to enable effective implementation.
- Tools could stimulate specific conservation actions through improved coordination and stakeholder engagement.
- Apply MSP4BIO tools in planning and integrating diverse activities in multifunctional marine zones.

VALIDATION AND IMPROVEMENT

Reflection of MSP/MPA community needs 9

Yes, the results correspond to the main needs and challenges filling knowledge gaps of the community. MSP4BIO helps facilitating policy integration at the local level.

The applicability should be further examined in test sites to validate the above mentioned statements.

Integration in local or national MSP/MPA processes 10

A solid foundation and enhanced communication now enable smoother integration into key local and national processes. MSP4BIO results could support in the implementation of strict protection, MPA management and knowledge of VME in the local area of the CoP.

The underlying structure of administrations and the fear of change could derail the adoption of new policies.

Areas for improvement 11

- Develop new environmental indicators (e.g. functionality, climate sensitivity).
- Strengthen interdisciplinary skills for territorial management.
- Share and present results proactively to the public.
- Hold open discussions with stakeholders to align results with policy.

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Annex C: List of all dissemination activities in MSP4BIO project (internal reporting template)

Dissemination and communication activity	Number (Insert new row for each activity)	Date / Date Range	Name of event	Title of the communication activity [if you gave a presentation e.g. oral or poster please give the title and authors]	Type of Estimated Persons reached in the context of the dissemination and communication activities [Scientific Community (higher education, research)] (SC) [Industry] (Ind.) [Civil Society] (CS) [General Public] (GP) [Policy Makers] (PM) [Medias] (M) [Investors] (Inv.) [Customers] (C) [Others] (O)	Total Estimated Number of persons reached	Used funding amount EUR	Work Package Number (include project WP number(s))	Beneficiaries (List the contributing beneficiaries and indicate the lead in bold font format)	Name of Partner / Beneficiary Completing Each Row	Name of Person Completing Each Row										
												SC	Ind.	CS	GP	PM	M	Inv.	C	O	
Introduction Presentation of MSP4BIO	1	06 October 2022	Steering Committee meeting of the EUSBRs Policy Area Spatial Planning	Oral presentation (MSP4BIO Project, Kemal Pinarbasi)			12						12	350,00€	WP5, WP6 and WP7		HELCOM	Kemal Pinarbasi			
Introduction Presentation of MSP4BIO	2	29 September 2022	Annual Forum of EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region	Oral presentation (MSP4BIO Project, Kemal Pinarbasi)		5			5				10	50,00€	WP5, WP6 and WP7		HELCOM	Kemal Pinarbasi			
Introduction Presentation of MSP4BIO	3	03 November 2022	Final event of MAREA project	Oral presentation (MSP4BIO Project, Kemal Pinarbasi)	25								25	0,00	WP5, WP6 and WP7		HELCOM	Kemal Pinarbasi			
Presentation on EBA MSP including a reference to MSP4BIO	4	13 October 2022	Final event of MSPMED	Oral presentation (no ppt)	50								50	80,00€	WP7		WWF	Mauro Randone			
Participation to the 3rd Community of Practice workshop on EBA in MSP of eMSP project	5	02 December 2022	the 3rd Community of Practice workshop on EBA in MSP of eMSP project	Discussion on a mutual workshop	20	10							30	0	WP6, WP7		HELCOM	Kemal Pinarbasi			
Introduction Presentation of MSP4BIO and synergies	6	26 January 2023	BLUE4ALL kick-off meeting	UTARTU talked about MSP4BIOs synergies with BLUE4ALL.													UTARTU	Liisi Lees			
Introduction Presentation of MSP4BIO	7	20 January 2023	didactic visit	oral presentation MSP4BIO	14								14	0	WP7		NIMRD	Mariana Golumbeanu			
Introduction Presentation of MSP4BIO	8	08 February 2023	Second Joint Workshop Romania	Discussion on a mutual workshop - Republic of Moldova in #blackseaconnect! Hosted by Institutul National de Cercetare-Dezvoltare Marina "Grigore Antipa" INCDM and jointly run together with INCD GeoEcoMar and the Universitatea Pedagogică de Stat Ion Creangă din Republica Moldova	32	4	4	6	2				48	0	WP7		NIMRD	Alina Spinu/Mariana Golumbeanu			
Participation at the 3rd International Conference on Marine/Maritime Spatial Planning, Barcelona, Spain	9	22 - 23 November 2022	3rd International Conference on Marine/Maritime Spatial Planning	Fire-side talk at the MSP4BIO booth (Margarita Stancheva): the Black Sea perspective and how important is cross-border planning									0	663 Euro	WP7; WP5		CCMS	Margarita Stancheva			
Promotion of 'MSP4Bio' in the framework of the EU Interreg Italy-Croatia project (with PAPI/RAC as project partner)	10	09 February 2023	4th Thursday CREATIVE Talks Webinar - 'Maritime Spatial Planning in a Changing Climate'	Ivan Sekovski introduced the project and encouraged the participants to sign up for the 'MSP4Bio' newsletter	89	17	13	17	60			#	213	/	WP7		PAPI/RAC	Tea Marasović			
Introduction presentation of MSP4BIO - first insights of the T5.1 and WP3 outputs	11	17 March 2023	Paddle project final conference	MSP4BIO presentation				x					0		WP7; WP5		Cerema	Neil Alloncle			
Oral presentation Msp4Bio project and 5.1 results	12	24- 27 April 2023	3rd Congreso Iberoamericano de Gestión Integrada de Áreas Litorales (GIAL 2023)	Planificación espacial marina y gestión de áreas marinas protegidas. Análisis consultivo para el caso									300		WP7; WP5		UCA	Javier Onetti			
Oral presentation Msp4Bio project and 5.1 results	13	15-17 March 2023	The International Congress on Sustainable Social Development (ICOSSOD23)	Proyecto Horizon MSP4BIO: Planificación espacial marina y áreas marinas protegidas. el caso de									50		WP7; WP5		UCA	Javier Sanabria			
Promotion of 'MSP4Bio' in the framework of the Transboundary CAMP Otranto project (with PAPI/RAC as the project coordinator - UNEP/MAP system)	14	11 May 2023	CAMP Otranto ICZM & MSP workshop /Bindsidi, Italy	Potential Transboundary Implementation of ICZM and MSP	10			10	10				30		WP7		PAPI/RAC	Tea Marasović			
Promotion of 'MSP4Bio' in the framework of the UNEP/MAP system	15	12 May 2023	Meeting of PAPI/RAC Focal Points 2023 / Split, Croatia	Marine Spatial Planning withing the Barcelona Convention System (Marina Marković)					16			#	28		WP7		PAPI/RAC	Tea Marasović			
presentation at 4th ESP Europe Conference	16	11 October 2022	4th Ecosystem Services Partnership Europe Conference	Oral presentation; Integrative and data-driven assessment of ecosystem services under alternative									400				UTARTU	Liisi Lees			
Marea project final seminar "Sustainable planning and governance for marine and coastal area" http://marea.balticseaportal.net/2022/10/05/marea-project-final-seminar/	17	02 November 2022	MAREA final seminar	Oral presentation; Main modelling outcomes and future directions (Francisco R. Barboza)									50				UTARTU	Liisi Lees			
Marea (Interreg Central Baltic) project final seminar "Sustainable planning and governance for marine and coastal area" http://marea.balticseaportal.net/2022/10/05/marea-project-final-seminar/	18	03 November 2022	MAREA final seminar	Oral presentation; Joint testing of the portal and active discussion (Francisco R. Barboza)									50				UTARTU	Liisi Lees			
Seminar	19	21 February 2023	Seminar at Environmental and Marine Biology at Åbo Akademi University	Invited talk on Ecosystem Services modelling and PW4B at the Åbo Akademi University for researchers									20				UTARTU	Liisi Lees			
Collaboration meeting	20	24 April 2023	Project Meeting	Teams meeting (Jonne Kotta). Development of a common solution for three cumulative impact									5				UTARTU	Liisi Lees			
Conference	21	14-15 March 2023	VELMU conference	Invited keynote covering multiple aspects of sustainability and sea management https://www.svke.fi/en-									100				UTARTU	Liisi Lees			
Conference	22	05 August 2023	Conference on best ideas and practices for implementing climate and energy plans for local authorities	Invited talk covering climate change, invasive species and marine management									100				UTARTU	Liisi Lees			

Seminar	23	06 August 2023	Seminar at Aqua Nbs, SDU University Denmark	Invited talk on Cumulative Impact Assessment and PW4B (Francisco R. Barboza)																	10						UTARTU	Liisi Lees
Collaboration meeting	24	08 August 2023	ReMAP - MSP4BIO CIA collaboration	Development of a common solution for three cumulative impact assessment tools. Share data and invited talk on Cumulative Impact Assessment and PW4B. https://narnu.ut.ee/et/sisu/teaduskonv																	5						UTARTU	Liisi Lees
Conference	25	24 August 2023	Blue economy conference in Pärnu, Estonia	Invited talk on Cumulative Impact Assessment and PW4B. https://narnu.ut.ee/et/sisu/teaduskonv																	0						UTARTU	Liisi Lees
workshop	26	04 October 2023	EUSBSR Annual Forum Workshop, Workshop 5: The EUSBSR as an important facilitator of the Mission	Presentation on citizen engagement in Mission Ocean, Horizon Europe																	0						UTARTU	Liisi Lees
training	27	14 September 2023	ADRIENNE+ training on use of the PlanWise4Blue portal	Training course on the use of the decision support platform PlanWise4Blue for scientists.																	20						UTARTU	Liisi Lees
Workshop	28	16 November 2023	Workshop: Safeguarding Biodiversity	Strengthening Marine Protected Area Networks, policy coherence and community involvement																	100						UTARTU	Liisi Lees
workshop	29	25 January 2024	ReMAP - North West Med stakeholder workshop	MSP4BIO - ESE perspectives in the NW MED																	30	WP4, WP5					CEREMA	Neil Alloncle
workshop	30	25 November 2022	Conference on the Canary Islands Coastal Marine Area: Planning and Governance	In the context of MSP-OR Project the event was held in Lazarote to promote MSP discussion in Canary																	20	all					UAc	Débora Gutierrez
Course	31	17- 28 July 2023	course in MSP to Master students.	BLENDED INTENSIVE PROGRAMME IN MARITIME SPATIAL PLANNING PRACTICE																	20	all					UAc and UCA	Helena Calado, Camila Pegorelli, Javier
workshop Oral presentation MSP4Bio project CoP	32	6-8 February 2024	2nd INTERNATIONAL REGINA-MSP WORKSHOP	MSP4BIO_MSP_OR_CoP																	30	WP4, WP5					UAc	Débora Gutierrez
workshop Oral presentation MSP4Bio project CoP	33	12 February 2024	MED CoP interaction																								UAc	Helena Calado
Interview	34	01 May 2023	Newspaper issue - Jornal Correio dos Açores	O Ordenamento das Zonas Costeiras é fundamental e tem que ser doseado com algum bom senso																							UAc	Helena Calado
Newspaper	35	07 October 2023	Newspaper issue - Jornal Correio dos Açores	Uma Viagem pelos Açores com Destino ao Planeamento Espacial Marinho																							UAc	Helena Calado
Newspaper	36	27 September 2022	Newspaper issue - Jornal Correio dos Açores	Projecto europeu para a sustentabilidade dos oceanos azorais e do mundo																							UAc	Helena Calado
Newspaper	37	30 November 2023	Newspaper issue - Jornal Correio dos Açores	Workshop em cartografia participativa																							UAc	Helena Calado e Débora Gutierrez
Science news portal	38	17 October 2022	Newspaper issue - Novaator	Estonian marine scientist mapping app promotes sustainable usage of the sea (original title in Estonian)																			WP3				UTARTU	Liisi Lees
Workshop Trade-Offs	39	25 June 2024	Newspaper issue																			0 WP4					UAc and SPro	Helena Calado and Débora Gutierrez and
Seminar	40	13 June 2024	Seminar Cadiz	SEMINARIO INTERNACIONAL LA ECONOMIA AZUL EN LAS ISLAS AZORES Mesa redonda: Economía	30																30	WP4					UAc and UCA	Helena Calado and Débora Gutierrez and
General project communication / brief presentation of the MSP4BIO project	41	07 June 2024	Course: "MSP in the Mediterranean: from theory to practice"	(during the training course on MSP organised by PAP/RAC in Ankara, Republic of Türkiye, in collaboration	18										4						22	WP 7					PAP/RAC	Tea Marasović
General project communication / brief presentation of the MSP4BIO project	42	12-13 June 2024	Course: "MSP in the Mediterranean: from theory to practice"	(during the training course on MSP organised by PAP/RAC in Ankara, Republic of Türkiye, in collaboration with the Ministry of Environment	14	3					30				3						50	WP 7					PAP/RAC	Tea Marasović
Oral presentation Msp4Bio project in a Conference	43	27 September 2024	EUNICoast online conference	Débora Gutierrez presented Improved Science-based maritime spatial planning to safeguard and restore biodiversity in a coherent	20																200	all					UAc	Débora Gutierrez
Workshop Cadiz, CoP meeting	44	25 April 2025	Cop interaction Cadiz																								UCA, Uac	Camila Pegorelli Gomes
MPA/MSP Oral Presentation (Deliverable4.4)	45	12 July 2025	MPAinMSP Conference	Integrating MPA and MSP processes																	100	WP4					UAc and SPro	Débora Gutierrez/ Ivana (resent)
MSP4BIO project presented	46	05 May 2025	4th MSP Working group meeting	MSP in the Barcelona Convention - key findings and relevant outputs of MSP4BIO were briefly presented	5						15										20	WP 7					PAP/RAC	Marina Markovic
MSP4BIO project presented	47	06 May 2025	PAP/RAC Focal points meeting in Athens								30										30	WP 7					PAP/RAC	Marina Markovic